

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group Meeting, 19th January 2024

Present:

- Advisory Group: Fran Callaghan (MU); Edie Davis (SFI); Caleb Derven (UL); Jenny O'Neill (HEAnet); Kevin Kiely (TCD); Andrew Simpson (RCSI)
- OpenAIRE: Natalia Manola; Ioanna Grypari; Leonidas Pispiringas
- IReL: Jack Hyland (Chair), Catherine Ferris (Project Manager), Aaron Binchy (Minutes)

Apologies: Susan Reilly (IReL)

Jack formally welcomed Jenny O'Neill, who is replacing Eoin Kenny on the Advisory Group.

1. **Minutes** of meeting 27th October 2023: <https://zenodo.org/records/10105024>. **Approved 7th November 2023**
2. **Matters Arising and Action Points:**

Outstanding Action Points from 27th October:

a) OpenAIRE: to provide screenshots showing how deliverables meet tender specifications (focusing on those detailed in the comments to the draft Inception Report).

Action: OpenAIRE will send this with the presentation for the minutes (Appendix 1)

b) OpenAIRE: to deliver detailed documentation for RFOs and RPOs on what constitutes measures like findability, open access etc.

Done: OpenAIRE addressed this in their presentation.

c) OpenAIRE: to deliver detailed instructions for researchers on all aspects of the ORCID functionality: claiming, how this impacts these research outputs on the Monitor, logging in with ORCID and logging in with other credentials etc.

Done: OpenAIRE addressed this in their presentation.

d) Advisory Group: to define procedure for how dashboard managers will be assigned.

Action: Catherine to initiate the process and communicate the timeline to impact the draft Monitor on launch in January.

Done: <https://app.onlinesurveys.jisc.ac.uk/s/maynoothuniversity/national-open-access-monitor-dashboard-manager-application-form>

(e) Action: Catherine to provide the results of the stakeholder survey with the final confirmed list to OpenAIRE and Zenodo on 10th November.

Done: <https://zenodo.org/records/10100896>

(f) Action: OpenAIRE to update the draft *National Open Access Report, Ireland* by 15th November and provide to Catherine for distribution.

Done: <https://zenodo.org/records/10136296>

(g) Action: OpenAIRE to prepare mockups of visualisations for what it would look like to (a) not identify green as “open access” without an open license and (b) identifying all green as “open access”, but distinguishing between green with open license and green without open license.

Done: <https://zenodo.org/records/10478761>

(h) Action: Advisory Group to give feedback on the OpenAIRE mockups and agree on how green will be represented in the Report and Monitor.

Done: <https://zenodo.org/records/10478761>

3. **OpenAIRE presentation (Appendix 2) of National Open Access Monitor, Ireland Report (Appendix 3)**

4. **Advisory Group feedback on National Open Access Monitor, Ireland Report**

Action: OpenAIRE to revise language on pre-prints to reflect that they are not peer-reviewed (compared to AAM)

Actions on APCs:

- OpenAIRE to further address low level of data on APCs from OpenAPC in the report.
- OpenAIRE to provide a report to with an extrapolation exercise of APC costs with further analysis, to be delivered within the next month.
- OpenAIRE to organise a webinar with OpenAPC for show how institutions can share APC data.

Action: OpenAIRE to clarify in the text that while FAIR originated in data management it has been borrowed for these purposes.

Action: OpenAIRE to clarify, under *2.2.1 Access Rights*, that “Not available” is due to lack of data from the aggregator and does not reflect open access status; and to update to “unspecified access rights”.

Action: OpenAIRE to clarify publisher licenses (e.g. TDM) in the report and the methodology for how OpenAIRE are deciding if those licenses are open

Action: OpenAIRE to update report that there is a potential (based on research by Fran) that some organisations might not be exposing license metadata via OAI-PMH and that this may be contributing to the high numbers of *green without license* and warrants further investigation.

Action: OpenAIRE to update all references to AHSS.

Action: OpenAire to revise the *Methodological Concern* regarding NORF's definition of publicly-funding, to focus on the impact rather than the "concern" in the application of the definition.

Action: The Advisory Group agreed that, in response to a comment in the Report document, it is not necessary to update the report to include cross-country trends. OpenAIRE to action all other comments and questions in the annotated *National Open Access Report, Ireland* document (Appendix 3)

5. OpenAIRE presentation and demo of draft National Open Access Monitor, Ireland

6. Advisory Group feedback on draft National Open Access Monitor, Ireland

Action: OpenAIRE to improve, under Browse Research Produces, identification of Bronze articles (e.g. change "OA Route" to "Access Route"). Bronze should not be displayed as an OA route.

Action: OpenAIRE to make documentation for Researchers clearer. It is unclear currently that under Browse Research Products, not all of a researcher's activity will be displayed. Only content identified by OpenAIRE as affiliated with an Irish organisation appears here.

Action: OpenAire to provide a report on the Data Sources of Green Without Licence. This will not be included in the Monitor, but will be used to assist stakeholders in identifying areas which can be targeted for improvement.

Action: OpenAIRE to update default sorting on RPO and RFO dashboards to Number of Publications (instead of alphabetical)

The Advisory Group agreed:

Action: OpenAIRE to provide presentation slides and outstanding action point (a) by Monday 22nd January.

Action: OpenAIRE to update Monitor (as per presentation) by 7th February, for launch and distribution.

Action: OpenAIRE to provide updated Report for review by 8th February 2024

Action: Catherine to review updated Report. Advisory Group agreed that Catherine can approve Report for publication.

Action: OpenAire and Catherine to schedule a meeting to plan engagement strategy

Action: Catherine to check back with Advisory Group on week of 12th February to see if the Advisory Group would like a meeting with OpenAIRE for additional feedback on the Monitor.

Action: Aaron to send draft minutes by 23rd January. Advisory Group and OpenAIRE to review, update and approve by 30th January; no response will be taken as approval of the minutes.

National Open Access Report for Ireland

Requirements and breakdown charts screenshots

Notes for the screenshots

- Many of the screenshots are sourced from the National Monitor, although equivalent indicators are also present in the RPO & RFO Monitors.
- Screenshots for specific RPO/RFO/Researcher/Repository indicators have been obtained from their respective Monitors.
- The indicators in all the Monitors are broken down in various ways based on specific requirements. In the screenshots, we primarily used the year breakdown, but we also utilized other breakdowns as needed to meet the requirements. (e.g., Fields of Science (FoS) - breakdown for subjects).

M12. The Monitor MUST enable both point-in-time and longitudinal monitoring of the open access status of Irish publications.

- Three main components that enable longitudinal and point-in-time monitoring of Open Science uptake
 - Indicator Visualizations: Track Open Science trends over time.
 - Historical Snapshots: View progress through data snapshots.
 - Time Range Filter: Focus on specific publication years.
- Gain insights and monitor Open Science in Ireland.

M12. The Monitor MUST enable both point-in-time and longitudinal monitoring of the open access status of Irish publications.

Indicator Visualizations: Track Open Science trends over time.

Repository OA vs Publisher OA Trends

PR Publications

Green vs Gold vs Hybrid OA Trends

PR Publications

Unrealised OA Trends

hots

M12. The Monitor MUST enable both point-in-time and longitudinal monitoring of the open access status of Irish publications.

Time Range Filter: Focus on specific publication years.

Filters

2018 - 2022 ×

Time range Clear

2018
-
2022
➤

This year |
 Last 5 years |
 Last 10 years

Field of Science

03 Medical And Health ...

M12. The Monitor MUST enable both point-in-time and longitudinal monitoring of the open access status of Irish publications.

Longitudinal: Historical Snapshots. View progress through monthly data snapshots. Here the first month of the Monitor is visualized. Each month there will be a new column with the respective visualisation for each chart.

M13. The Monitor MUST identify embargoed and immediate open access.

- Gold and Hybrid OA publications are available immediately, providing instant access upon publication.
- Green OA with a licence can also be immediate OA, but this depends on whether the article is submitted to a repository at the time of its publication and in its version of record (VoR).
- Embargoed OA articles are only marked as 'embargoed' in the metadata until the embargo period expires.

M13. The Monitor MUST identify embargoed and immediate open access. Text from report samples

Immediate vs embargoed OA by Fields of Science (FoS) level 1

M14. The Monitor MUST identify repository-mediated and publisher-mediated open access. 1 screenshot

- The Monitor identifies publisher-mediated and repository-mediated open access.
- OpenAIRE retains metadata from all contributing data sources, even after deduplication.
- This enables identification by data source type (publisher, repository) and access rights of publications.

B1. The Monitor MUST show to what extent Irish scholarly publications resulting from publicly funded research are immediately openly available by default and are accessible on an ongoing basis. Publicly funded in this context is defined as “Publicly funded research is research undertaken in whole or in part via publicly funded resourcing or remuneration, e.g., salaries, grants, contracts, etc.”

- We identify publicly funded research: We identify the sources of publicly funded research as explicitly stated by:
- the RPOs/RFOs that participated in the National OA Monitor survey
- The RFOs that have been characterised as Governmental type in the Open Funder Registry.

Publicly funded filter in the Monitor

- 01 Natural Sciences (45,774)
- 02 Engineering And Tech... (44,082)
- 0301 Basic Medicine (42,452)

[View all >](#)

Publicly funded [Clear](#)

All	Yes	No
-----	-----	----

Funder

- Science Foundation Ireland (13,073)
- European Commission (12,629)
- [Irish Research Council \(2,752\)](#)

Filters [Clear All](#)

Type [Clear](#)

- Publications
- Research Data
- Research Software
- Other Research Products

Document Type

- Article (173,994)
- Conference Object (23,680)
- Other Literature Type (22,995)
- Part Of Book Or Chapter... (16,488)
- Preprint (8,158)
- Thesis (6,114)

[View all >](#)

Peer reviewed [Clear](#)

[Advanced search](#)

216,523 Research Products

[DOWNLOAD RESULTS](#) [DATA DUMP](#)

IRISH NATIONAL MONITOR PUBLICATIONS × PEER REVIEWED: YES × PUBLICLY FUNDED: YES ×

Results per page
10

Sort by
Relevance

1 2 3 4 5 >

The Portuguese Participation in the Actifcare (Access to Timely Formal Care in Dementia) European Study: Preliminary Results of Systematic Reviews, Qualitative and Quantitative Data

[Publication](#) >> Article • 2017 • Cambridge University Press (CUP) • Publicly funded

Authors: [Manuel Gonçalves-Pereira](#); [Maria J. Marques](#); [Conceição Balsinha](#); [Teresa Alves dos Reis](#); +13 Authors

DOI: [10.1016/j.eurpsy.2017.01.1089](#)

IntroductionIn the context of untimely access to community formal services, unmet needs of persons with dementia (PwD) and their carers may compromise their quality of life.Objectives/aimsThe Actifcare EU-JPND project ([www.actifcare.eu](#)) focuses on access to and (non) utilization of dementia formal care in eight...

[European Psychiatry](#) | [Link to](#) | [Share](#) | [Cite](#) | [Claim](#)

[OA Routes](#) | [0](#)

Diversity, asymmetry and the quest for consensus

[Publication](#) >> Article • 1998 • Elsevier BV • Publicly funded

Authors: [D.G. Pringle](#);

DOI: [10.1016/S0920-9961\(97\)00044-0](#)

B2. The Monitor MUST be able to identify the percentage of OA availability and the progress of this over time, with drill-down functionality in a number of facets including funding agency, Irish HEI, corresponding author affiliation, year of publication, subject or keyword, publisher, grant award ID, or arbitrary combinations of these.

- The Monitor employs a two-fold approach to data presentation and exploration.
 - Breakdowns: The dashboard is configured to showcase detailed breakdowns using key categorizations.
 - Filters: To complement the breakdowns, the dashboard will integrate additional filters allowing the user to further refine the data. The filters that are incorporated in the pilot for the Monitor include year range, FoS and publicly-funded.
- Employing a combination of detailed breakdowns with select additional filters, the dashboard is designed for optimal drill-down functionality. This ensures that users can probe into specific data points while the interface remains user-friendly and uncluttered.

B2. The Monitor MUST be able to identify the percentage of OA availability and the progress of this over time, with drill-down functionality in a number of facets including funding agency, Irish HEI, corresponding author affiliation, year of publication, subject or keyword, publisher, grant award ID, or arbitrary combinations of these.

- Filtering in the Browse Research Outputs sections includes:
 - RFO
 - year of publication (range)
 - FoS
 - country of affiliated RPO
 - language
 - data source
 - Research Community
 - Type of research output: Options include peer-reviewed publications (preselected as the default filter), all publications, datasets, software, and other research products.

Filters [Clear All](#)

Type [Clear](#)

- Publications
- Research Data
- Research Software
- Other Research Products

Document Type

- Article (274,474)
- Other Literature Type (36,526)
- Conference Object (34,179)
- Part Of Book Or Chapter... (21,873)
- Preprint (12,197)
- Thesis (6,155)

[View all >](#)

Peer reviewed [Clear](#)

- All Yes No

Access

- Open Access
- Closed Access
- Restricted
- Open Source
- Embargo

OA Routes

Green

- All Yes No

OA Color

- Bronze (119,625)
- Gold (50,063)
- Hybrid (37,709)

In a Diamond OA journal

- All Yes No

Year range

1800 - 2034 >

[This year](#) | [Last 5 years](#)

[Last 10 years](#)

Field of Science

- 03 Medical And Health ... (135,461)
- Null (119,710)
- 0302 Clinical Medicine (89,024)
- 01 Natural Sciences (62,582)
- 0301 Basic Medicine (61,965)
- 02 Engineering And Tech... (57,673)

[View all >](#)

Publicly funded

- All Yes No

Funder

- European Commission (17,228)
- Science Foundation Ireland (16,675)
- Irish Research Council (4,076)
- National Institutes Of H... (4,066)
- Wellcome Trust (3,096)
- UK Research And Innovation (2,923)

[View all >](#)

Source

- Europe PubMed Central (35,809)
- Trinity's Access To Res... (20,336)
- Maynooth University EPr... (12,600)
- Access To Research At N... (10,016)
- ArXiv.org E-Print Archive (9,385)
- NARCIS (8,464)

Research community

- Knowmad Institut (110,363)
- TUNet (14,646)
- Netherlands (13,103)
- Digital Humanities And ... (11,048)
- Energy Research (10,347)
- Social Science And Human... (9,777)

[View all >](#)

15

Filter in the Monitor & Browse Research Outputs

- The corresponding author filter has not been utilised due to its low coverage.
- Grant awards are shown in the respective RFO Monitors.

Requirements and breakdown charts screensh

Filters

Time range

1800 - 2034 >

[This year](#)

[Last 5 years](#)

[Last 10 years](#)

Field of Science

- 03 Medical And Health ...
- Null
- 0302 Clinical Medicine
- 01 Natural Sciences
- 0301 Basic Medicine
- 02 Engineering And Tech...

[View all >](#)

Publicly funded

- All Yes No

C1. KPI: Usage by Irish Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) to measure funded research outputs.

- **Comprehensive Research Output Coverage**
 - OpenAIRE integrates project data into the OpenAIRE Graph to ensure comprehensive coverage of funded research outputs.
- **Funding Source Identification**
 - OpenAIRE's funding classifiers analyze publication abstracts to identify funding sources, linking research outputs to projects for inclusion in the Monitor.
- **Customized Views for Organizations**
 - RPOs and RFOs access additional organization indicators and research output browsing through their profiles.
- **Benchmarking and Visualization**
 - Benchmarking metrics and visualizations allow comparison across organizations and countries.

National Benchmarking

Top Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

by number of funded PR publications

PR Publications by country (sorted by Repository OA)

Peer Reviewed Publications

by Access Rights, by country

Green vs Gold vs Hybrid OA

PR Publications by country (sorted by Green OA w/ License)

Top Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) by number of PR publications

Cross RPOs

Top Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) by number of PR publications

Cross RFOs

C2. KPI: Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to measure OA.

- RPOs & RFOs can visit their respective monitors to discover the respective indicators for their organisation to measure OA and OA uptake. As explicitly defined by screenshots and indicators for the National Monitor in M12 - M16, B2, C1. 3 As an example we present screenshots from RPOs & RFOs Monitors.

RPOs

RFOs

Top Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

by Publisher Mediated OA (Gold & Hybrid OA)

Top Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

by Publisher Mediated OA (Gold & Hybrid OA)

Top Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

by number of OA w/ License PR publications

Top Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

by number of OA w/ License PR publications

C3. Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to promote/enable OA compliance

- The Monitor will include indicators and functionalities for organizations to track their OA policy uptake.
- OpenAIRE also will offer various open access indicators at the publication-level (when browsing) such as access rights, OA classes, etc.
- Researchers will be able to view these easily in their own profile, to assess where they stand.

The Monitor will include indicators and functionalities for organizations to track their OA policy uptake.

RPOs

RFOs

Plan S Compliant PR Publications Trends

- in Diamond OA Journal
- under Transformative Agreement
- not Plan S compliant
- Gold OA with APCs
- in Transformative Journal

Plan S Compliant PR Publications

- in Diamond OA Journal
- under Transformative Agreement
- not Plan S compliant
- Gold OA with APCs
- in Transformative Journal

OpenAIRE also will offer various open access indicators at the publication-level (when browsing) such as access rights, OA classes, etc.

PR Publications

by Access Rights by FoS (level 1)

Repository OA vs Publisher OA

PR Publications by Fields of Science - FoS (level 1)

Green vs Gold vs Hybrid OA

by FoS (level 1)

Researchers will be able to view these easily in their own profile, to assess where they stand.

29 research outcomes
Queen's University Belfast, Trinity College Dublin, University College Cork, University College Dublin, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-...>

79%
Open Access

MONITOR
BROWSE RESEARCH PRODUCTS

Overview

Publications

26

Peer Reviewed (PR) Publications

26

OA w/ Licence PR Publications

18

Gold OA PR Publications

2

Hybrid OA PR Publications

5

Green OA w/ license PR Publications

1

Access Rights Trends

for PR Publications

Year	Open Access w/ Licence	Open Access w/o Licence	Embargo	Restricted	Closed Access	not available
2007	1	1	0	0	0	0
2012	1	0	0	1	0	0
2013	1	0	0	0	0	0
2015	1	0	0	0	0	0
2016	3	0	0	0	0	0
2017	1	0	0	1	1	0
2018	5	1	0	0	1	0
2019	1	0	0	0	0	0
2020	2	0	0	0	0	0
2021	2	0	0	0	0	0

PR Publications

by Access Rights by FoS (level 1)

FoS (level 1)	Open Access w/ Licence	Open Access w/o Licence	Embargo	Restricted	Closed Access	not available
01 natural sciences	14	2	0	1	4	0
02 engineering and technology	1	0	0	0	0	0
03 medical and health sciences	7	1	0	1	0	0
04 agricultural and veterinary sciences	1	0	0	1	0	0

<> EMBED
<> EMBED

C4. Usage by government departments to measure and report on OA compliance as overall % of Irish research publications.

- The National View/Landing Page of the Irish Monitor (M11) will provide cross-country benchmarking and key within-country indicators, broken down by different facets of interest that would supply Government Departments various data and visualizations of interest for reporting.

Cross-Country Indicators

Peer Reviewed Publications

by Access Rights, by country

Unrealised Open Access

PR Publications by country (sorted by Closed Access)

Repository OA vs Publisher OA

PR Publications by country (sorted by Repository OA)

Green vs Gold vs Hybrid OA

PR Publications by country (sorted by Green OA w/ License)

C5. Demonstrable engagement by researchers in using OA Monitoring when assessing their OA compliance.

- **Publication-Level OA Indicators**
 - OpenAIRE provides open access indicators at the publication level in the Monitor's research output browsing section.
- **Easy Access for Researchers**
 - Researchers can view access rights, OA classes, and more in their own profiles, simplifying compliance assessment.
- **Organizational Insights**
 - RPO and RFO profiles aggregate indicators at the organization level, facilitating the identification of areas that may require attention

Publication level Indicators

A Pleistocene legacy structures variation in modern seagrass ecosystems

Publication » Article • 2022 • United States, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, United Kingdom, France, Norway, Spain • Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences • Publicly funded • NSF | Collaborative Research: G..., NSF | Biodiversity and Complex ..., NSF | Collaborative Research: G... +1 projects

Authors: J. Emmett Duffy; John J. Stachowicz; Pamela L. Reynolds; Kevin A. Hovel; +37 Authors

DOI: [10.1073/pnas.2121425119](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2121425119) PMID: [35939678](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35939678/) PMC: [PMC9371661](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PMC9371661/)

HANDLE: [10400.1/19221](https://doi.org/10.4000.1/19221), [11250/3034740](https://doi.org/10.11250/3034740), [11370/fd946662-a9df-4fcf-8cfc-2e9e51b4fd99](https://doi.org/10.11370/fd946662-a9df-4fcf-8cfc-2e9e51b4fd99)

Distribution of Earth's biomes is structured by the match between climate and plant traits, which in turn influences ecosystem processes and services. However, that climate-trait match can be disrupted by historical events, with lasting effects on ecosystem processes faster than...

- Green
- Hybrid

NARCIS |
 Link to |
 Share |
 Cite |
 Claim |
 OA Routes |
 9 |
 29

RPO level indicators

down charts screenshots

C6. Demonstrable use of OA Monitoring to inform and support strategic developments in the area of Open Science

- The Monitor:
 - Utilises metrics and indicators for the Open Access status of the Irish research output. (Open Access classes, APCs, Plan S & Transformative agreements).
 - Uses comparison and benchmarking charts across countries in the National Dashboard for RFOs and RPOs on broad aspects of monitoring OA.
 - Identifies the 'unrealised' OA of the Irish research and assess the "Closed access publications that are found Open in repositories" as well as the share of closed access publications.
- The performance of each institution and benchmarking against national peers is available.
- The "Browse Research Outputs" section includes, at the publication level, the "View XX Versions" links from all data sources containing the corresponding records, thus all OA versions of the research products.

Open Access Routes

Top Publishers

by Hybrid OA

Green vs Gold vs Hybrid OA Trends

PR Publications

APCs

Total APCs (EUR) Trends

PR Publications Trends

with APCs vs under Transformative Agreements

● with APCs ● under Transformative Agreements

Top 20 Journals

by Total APCs (EUR)

Plan S & Transformative agreements

Plan S Compliant PR Publications Trends

- in Diamond OA Journal
- under Transformative Agreement
- not Plan S compliant
- Gold OA with APCs
- in Transformative Journal

Top Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

by number of Plan S Compliant PR Publications

Browse Research Outputs

NARCIS
View all 13 versions
Link to
Share
Cite

A Pleistocene legacy structures variation in modern seagrass ecosystems

Publication » Article - 01 Aug 2022 - United States, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, United Kingdom, France, Norway, Spain - Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences - Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, volume 119 (issn: 0027-8424, eissn: 1091-6490) [Copyright policy](#) - Publicly funded - NSF | Collaborative Research: G., NSF | Biodiversity and Complex ... NSF | Collaborative Research: G., +1 projects

Authors: [J. Emmett Duffy](#), [John J. Stachowicz](#), [Pamela L. Reynolds](#), [Kevin A. Hovel](#), [Marlene Jahnke](#), [Erik E. Sotka](#), [Christoffer Boström](#); +34 Authors

DOI: [10.1073/pnas.2121425119](#) [□] PMID: [35939678](#) [□] PMC: [PMC9371661](#) [□]
 HANDLE: [10400.1/19221](#) [□], [11250/3034740](#) [□], [11370/fd946662-a9df-4fcf-8cfc-2e9e51b4fd99](#) [□], [10261/295724](#) [□]

Summary
Subjects
Metrics

Abstract
 Distribution of Earth's biomes is structured by the match between climate and plant traits, which in turn shape associated communities and ecosystem processes and services. However, that climate-trait match can be disrupted by historical events, with lasting ecosystem impacts. As Earth's environment changes faster than at any time in human history, critical questions are whether and how organismal traits and ecosystems can adjust to altered conditions. We quantified the relative importance of current environmental forcing versus evolutionary history in shaping the growth form (stature and biomass) and associated community of eelgrass (*Zostera marina*), a widespread foundation plant of marine ecosystems along Northern Hemisphere coastlines, which experienced major shifts in distribution and genetic composition during the Pleistocene. We found that eelgrass stature and biomass retain a legacy of the

than effects of current environmental forcing. Such historical lags in phenotypic acclimatization may constrain ecosystem adjustments to rapid anthropogenic climate change, thus altering predictions about the future functioning of ecosystems...

[View more](#) >

Countries
 United States, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, United Kingdom, France, Norway, Spain

Related Organizations

- Spanish National Research Council
- Spain

Funded by

NSF Collaborative Research: Global biodiversity and functioning of eelgrass ecosystems, NSF Biodiversity and Complex Forcing of Ecosystem Functioning in the Marine Foundation Species, Eelgrass: A Global Experimental Network, NSF Collaborative Research: Global biodiversity and functioning of eelgrass ecosystems, NSF Collaborative Research: Global biodiversity and functioning of eelgrass ecosystems

Related to Research communities

- [EU-CONEXUS](#) [□]
- [EUTOPIA Alliance](#) [□]
- [Energy Research](#) [□]
- [Netherlands](#) [□]

Other versions

13 Publications, Page 1 of 3

A Pleistocene legacy structures variation in modern seagrass ecosystems

Publication » Article - 2022 - English

HANDLE: [11370/fd946662-a9df-4fcf-8cfc-2e9e51b4fd99](#) [□]

Distribution of Earth's biomes is structured by the match between climate and plant traits, which in turn shape associated communities and ecosystem processes and services. However, that climate-trait match can be disrupted by historical events, with lasting ecosystem impacts. As Earth's environment changes faster than at any time in...

A Pleistocene legacy structures variation in modern seagrass ecosystems

Publication » Article - 2022 - English

Authors: [Duffy, J Emmett](#); [Stachowicz, John J](#); [Reynolds, Pamela L](#); [Hovel, Kevin A](#); +37 Authors

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DOI: [10.1073/pnas.2121425119](#) [□]

Distribution of Earth's biomes is structured by the match between climate and plant traits, which in turn shape associated communities and ecosystem processes and services. However, that climate-trait match can be disrupted by historical events, with lasting ecosystem impacts. As Earth's environment changes faster than at any time in...

C9. Usage by Irish national consortia to inform new OA publishing agreements and monitor existing agreements.

- The Monitor utilises Plan S compliance indicators, particularly focusing on the period 2021 onwards and publications:
 - published in Diamond OA journals
 - published under Transformative Agreements
 - published in Transformative Journals
 - follow the Gold OA route.
- While not exhaustive of all Plan S requirements, these factors provide insights into the evolving dynamics of OA publishing and assists in understanding how differently OA models and agreements are being adopted and integrated in line with Plan S principles.

C9. Usage by Irish national consortia to inform new OA publishing agreements and monitor existing agreements.

C10. Usage by publishers to monitor visibility of published content and analyse sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies.

- The Monitor displays key aspects of Open Science, with indicators on access rights and open access classes, also broken down by publishers.

Top Publishers

by number of PR publications

Top Publishers

by number of OA w/ Licence PR publications

Requirement

C10. Usage by publishers to monitor visibility of published content and analyse sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies.

Repository OA vs Publisher OA

PR Publications by Fields of Science - FoS (level 1)

Top Publishers

by Hybrid OA

Top Publishers

by Gold OA

Thank you!

 OpenAIRE
SCIENCE.SET FREE.

National Open Access Monitor, Ireland

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AGENDA

National Open Access Monitor, Ireland

Report

- Structure
- Baseline Analysis
- Data Evaluation & Challenges
- Recommendations

Platform

- Demo
- Improvements in progress
- Ensuring top data quality

Report

STRUCTURE

- **Executive Summary**
 - Key observations & insights
 - Main data challenges
 - Recommendations in brief
- **Introduction**
 - Background of the study
 - Objective and purpose of the report
 - General Methodological Approach (High-level overview)
- **Baseline Analysis**
 - Scholarly Production
 - Open & FAIR
 - Plan S
- **APCs & Transformative Agreements**
 - Main findings
- **Methodology**
 - Methodological specifics
- **Data Evaluation & Challenges**
- **Recommendations & Solutions**
 - Direct Improvement Strategies for the Monitor
 - Indirect Improvement Strategies
 - Long-Term Solutions

Conclusion

Appendix

Baseline Analysis Highlights

SCHOLARLY PRODUCTION

Irish publications

418,322

and % of Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications

329,308 (78,7%)

- Peer-Reviewed Publications

- **78.7%** of total, high **academic rigor** in Irish research.

- Trend Analysis

- **Steady increase** in peer-reviewed output from 2007 to 2020.

- Publication dip could be attributed to delays in indexing and reporting, **repository use** could improve this

- Reflects a **dynamic and growing research sector** in Ireland.

- Increased use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and digital repositories.

Clarifications / Report Changes

- We do not only consider publications after 2007.

Methodological issues to discuss

- peer-review

SCHOLARLY PRODUCTION

Leading Disciplines

- Clinical medicine and health sciences (**basic medicine, clinical medicine**)
- Natural sciences (**physical sciences, chemical sciences**)
- Engineering and technology (**electrical, electronic, information engineering and nano technology**)

Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences

- Smaller scale and exhibit focused, specialized research, indicate **niche expertise**.

Social Sciences and Humanities

- Display a rich **diversity** of research.

Methodological issues to discuss

- Under-representation of certain disciplines

SCHOLARLY PRODUCTION

	# Irish peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish peer-reviewed publications
Article	272,536	82.8%
Other literature type	36,521	11.1%
Conference object	34,368	10.5%
Part of book or chapter of book	22,172	6.7%
Preprint	12,097	3.7%
Thesis	6,156	1.9%
Book	1,152	0.3%

- **Articles** as the dominant type of publication
- **Journals** as the main source for peer-reviewed publications.
- **Digital shift:** presence of repositories
- **Mandates/policy** potential for impact

PR Publications
by data source type

Clarifications / Report Changes

- Pre-prints
- Include overall repository deposition?

OPEN & FAIR: ACCESS RIGHTS

	% OA with licence	% OA w/o licence	% Closed Access
Article	44.6%	13.8%	27.6%
Conference object	20.5%	32.3%	8%
Part of book or chapter of book	14.9%	16.8%	39.9%
Book	15.9%	38.4%	9.8%

- Open Access w/ licence **38.6%**

- goes up to **56.18%** if OA w/o licence included

- *Diverse licensing practices* **books** and **conference objects** highest share **w/o licence**

- **65.2%** in 2021 → growing trend towards licenced OA

- Closed Access: **26.3%** (**16.9%** in 2021), **parts of books** highest %

Unspecified Access: **17.07%** (**8%** in 2021)

- **Challenges** in fully transitioning to Open Access

Clarifications / Report Changes

- All analysis to emphasize recent years (2020 – 2022)

Methodological issues to discuss

- Licence requirement

OPEN & FAIR: ACCESS RIGHTS

Overall OA w/ licence rate

- Medical (44.3%)
- Natural (42.7%)
- Agricultural (39.4%)
- Social (35.5%)
- Engineering (36.4%)
- Humanities (25.1%)

2021 OA w/ licence rate

- Natural (76.7%)
- Agricultural (74%)
- Medical (71.7%)
- Engineering (67.4%)
- Social (62.6%)
- Humanities (51.5%)

OA rate **above** field average: **environmental engineering**

OA rate **below** field average: **Education, law, and political science**

OPEN & FAIR: OPEN ACCESS ROUTES

OA route	# Irish OA licenced peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish OA licenced peer-reviewed publications
Repository mediated OA (Green OA w/ licence)	8,483	6.7%
Publisher mediated OA (Gold OA)	48,795	38.4%
Publisher mediated OA (Hybrid OA)	38,113	30%

Repository-mediated vs publisher mediated OA

- Publisher-mediated dominant with 91.1% overall, 90.8% in 2021
- Repository mediated: 15.7% overall, 16.4% in 2021
 - Pick in 2018, 2019 has been decreasing
 - Repositories under-used
- Different picture if Green w/o Licence included

Methodological issues to discuss

- Licencing in repositories

OPEN & FAIR: OPEN ACCESS ROUTES

Repository OA vs Publisher OA

PR Publications by Fields of Science - FoS (level 1)

- **Medical lead in publisher-mediated OA**
- **Humanities highly engaged in repository-mediated OA.**
- **Data from 2007-2022**
 - **Steady increase in Green OA with Licence.**
 - **Peak in % Gold OA in 2020**
- **Hybrid % OA's significant rise post-2018**
 - **evolving OA policies, particularly Plan S principles.**

OPEN & FAIR: OPEN ACCESS ROUTES

	OA route	# Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence	% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence
Immediate OA	Green OA with licence	8,483	6.7%
	Gold OA	48,795	38.4%
	Hybrid OA	38,113	30%
	Embargo OA	84	0.07%

Immediate vs Embargo Open Access

Embargoed OA Articles → Complex to understand embargoed publications trends over time.

- Tracked as 'embargoed' only until the end of the embargo period.
- Low number (only 83) explicitly tagged as 'embargoed'.
- Historical snapshots will solve this

Green w/ licence & immediate OA

- Lack of consistent metadata on date of deposition and version type (VoR or AAM) in repositories.

OPEN & FAIR: OPEN ACCESS ROUTES

Unrealised OA	# Irish peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish peer-reviewed publications
Closed Access	86,516	26.3%
Green without Licence	72,042	21.9%
Bronze	122,397	37.2%

Unrealised OA

- Increase in **Bronze** and **Green without licence** → **growing, unrealised OA potential.**
- **Plateauing** trend in **Closed Access** publications.
- Encouraging or **automating proper licensing** in Green OA can enhance accessibility and usability.
- **Humanities & Arts, Social Sciences:** High ratio of Bronze to Green OA without licence, **favoring accessible but unlicensed publishing.**

OPEN & FAIR: FAIR

PR Publications

by licence type

PR publications with a CC licence

over time

Dominance of restrictive licences

Growing adoption of Creative Commons (CC) licences

Thematic repositories leading CC use

OPEN & FAIR: FAIR

Diversifying PIDs: Suggests a more **interconnected** digital ecosystem. Poses challenges for **managing** and **harmonizing** different PIDs.

Notable rise in **ORCID** usage: From **51.6%** (2007) to **72.4%** (2020), slight dip to 71.7% (2021).

Clarifications / Report Changes

- Error in report there are 10K PR publications without PID (it says 100%)

Methodological issues to discuss

- PIDs & peer-review

OPEN & FAIR: FAIR

PR Publications with Abstract

over time

% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publication with a valid URL in their metadata

45%

% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications that are ACCESSIBLE

33%

(full-text can be fetched from URL link)

% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications that are INTEROPERABLE

33%

(full-text is in a machine readable format)

High presence of abstracts in metadata (**over 90%**) indicates robust practices. **Quality and relevance** of abstracts need scrutiny.

33% OA PR pubs include link directly to the full-text PDF.
Potential for increased accessibility.

TENTATIVE

PLAN S

Irish Plan S Funders: Science Foundation Ireland 16,675 PR Publications

		# Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence post-2020	% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence post-2020 ²⁰
No APCs	In Diamond Journals	46	0.21%
	Under Transformative Agreements	1427	6.38%
	In Transformative Journals	1749	7.81%
Gold OA with APCs		12,467	55.7%

Increasing uptake of **Transformative Agreements and Journals**. Low presence in **Diamond Journals (0.21%)**, suggesting **underutilization**.

Social Sciences and Humanities benefiting from **Transformative** routes.

Clarifications / Report Changes

- TA data error (only partially integrated all #'s to be updated by next week)

Methodological issues to discuss

- Not Plan S compliant

APCS

Peer-Reviewed publications that incurred an APC	85,288
Peer-Reviewed publications under Transformative Agreement no APCs	1,477
Peer-Reviewed publications with APC data available from OpenAPC	1,194 (1.4% of all PR pubs with APCs)
Total APCs incurred from OpenAPC – unclear who covered the APC	EUR 2.2Mi
Average APC per publication	EUR 2,200
Average APC for Gold OA vs Hybrid OA	EUR 1,813 vs. EUR 2,756

Severe lack of data.

Decline after 2017 reporting disparity, or shift to Transformative Agreements.

High APCs in medical/scientific journals (e.g., Nature Communications, PLOS ONE).

Total APCs (EUR) Trends

Top 20 Journals by Total APCs (EUR)

Clarifications / Report Changes

- APC per publisher meaningful?

TENTATIVE

APCS & TRANSFORMATIVE AGREEMENTS

PR Publications Trends

with APCs vs under Transformative Agreements

PR Publications

with APCs vs under Transformative Agreements by FoS (level 2)

Significant increase in **2021**: **12.2%** of pubs with APCs covered.

Varied TA benefits across and within disciplines.

METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES TO DISCUSS

- **Under-representation** of certain disciplines and in a non-uniform way - **74.7% classified**
 - Under-representation of Total and of Closed Access
 - Hard to evaluate due to differences in publication timelines even though promising trends.
- **Licence requirement and Licencing in repositories**
 - Completely different picture if Green w/o licence considered OA – discussion last time pointed to automatic/assumed (?) licensing in repositories
- **PIDs & peer-review**
 - **Curated peer-reviewed list** OR **not gray literature** + DOI from Crossref – **all examples of articles with DOI from DataCite already classified as PR** – encourage users to flag mistakes

Data Evaluation & Challenges Highlights

Data Evaluation & Challenges

- **Metadata elements needed but not regularly shared**

- Date of deposit to repository
- VoR, AAM, etc (on occasion pre-print identified)
- Access rights at time of deposit
- Peer-review
- Corresponding author
- *Affiliation & proper funding acknowledgment (less)*

- **Crucial metadata elements with inconsistencies (dirty)**

- Affiliation (name alterations)
- Publisher
- Journal
- Licence
- URLs

- **Licence Reporting Complexities:** Difficulties in mapping licences to openness levels.
- **Funding and Output Links:** Need for improved RFO reporting.

Recommendations & Solutions

Recommendations & Solutions

Direct Improvement Strategies

Recommendation	Policy Makers	Publishers	RPOs	RFOs	Researchers	Institutional Repository Managers
Organisation Deduplication via OpenOrgs: regularly deduplicate RPO names and manage department/affiliated entity relationships ⁴⁶ .	X		X	X		
Join OpenAIRE: RFOs can join OpenAIRE by providing their project data for customized text mining and metadata enrichment ⁴⁷ .				X		
Registration to OpenAIRE PROVIDE: Register institutional data sources to OpenAIRE PROVIDE, follow the latest version of the OpenAIRE Guidelines, and use the Metadata Validator and Broker services for enhanced metadata quality ⁴⁸ .						X
Register with ORCID and Sync to Monitor: Register with ORCID and synchronize your ORCID and with Monitor accounts to keep both records current ⁴⁹ .					X	

Recommendation	Policy Makers	Publishers	RPOs	RFOs	Researchers	Institutional Repository Managers
Use Linking Functionality in OpenAIRE: Use Linking functionality to enrich connections within the Graph by linking research products to other researcher products, research communities or projects ⁴⁹ .	X	X	X	X	X	X
Engage with Monitor Dashboard & Provide Feedback: Interact with the Monitor dashboards and provide data quality feedback for continuous improvement.	X	X	X	X	X	X
Attend Engagement and Training Events: Participate in engagement and training events to stay informed about best practices and updates ⁵⁰ .	X	X	X	X	X	X
Reach Out for Help & Guidance: Contact the Monitor team for any issues or requests ⁵¹ .	X	X	X	X	X	X

Recommendations & Solutions

Indirect Improvement Strategies

• Policy Makers

- Mandate timely **research output deposition with standardized metadata**.
- Develop **discipline-specific OA policies** and **support mechanisms**.

• Publishers

- Implement consistent **metadata standards**.
- Share publication data openly, including **APCs**, **BPCs**, and **access rights**.
- Foster **transparency in licensing** and **metadata sharing**.

• Research Funding Organizations (RFOs)

- Guide on **accurate project outcome** reporting.
- Advocate for **transparency in APC/BPC** data.

• Researchers

- Consistently use of **ORCID iDs** and updating of **ORCID record**.

• Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)

- Update **publication records** regularly.
- Encourage standard **naming conventions** and **PID** use.
- Report **APCs/BPCs**.

• Institutional Repository Managers

- Follow **OpenAIRE guidelines** for metadata.

• Repository Managers (non-institutional)

- Maintain **robust metadata standardization** and **quality control**.
- Implement **automatic licensing** functionalities.

• All Stakeholders

- Engage in **training** on **metadata management** and **Open Science**.
- **Collaborate** to address metadata challenges and share solutions.

Recommendations & Solutions

Long-Term Solutions

- **Data Management Standards**

- Continuously update and improve metadata standards.
- Harmonize metadata and PID policies globally.
- Promote policies aligned with FAIR principles.

- **Data Preservation and Accessibility**

- Ensure adherence to FAIR principles.
- Upgrade repositories for durable data preservation.

- **Routine Metadata Audits**

- Regularly audit for metadata accuracy.
- Create collaborative platforms for metadata improvement.

- **Training and Development**

- Provide training in metadata management.
- Develop resources and feedback mechanisms for continuous learning.

- **Tailor strategies to address specific metadata challenges.**

- **Stay prepared for emerging trends in OA monitoring and data management.**

Platform

THE MONITOR

<https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/>

DEMO

TOWARDS A PRODUCTION QUALITY IRISH MONITOR

Work in Progress

What we are working on

- Repository Monitors
 - Bug in the Access Rights tab – latest by Feb 7 (expected earlier)
- Transformative Agreements
 - Incomplete data – – latest by Feb 7 (expected earlier)
- Filtering
 - with or without license filter when browsing results – next Graph update
- UI/UX improvements underway
 - Search, resources and help, splash page

To Discuss

- Domain
 - <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/>
- Tech support person
- Use of survey
 - RPOs w/ PIDs, repositories, publicly-funded
 - Authoritative lists of organisations and funders
- Engagement strategy

Thank you!

National Open Access
Monitor Ireland

Report

Executive Summary¹

Ireland is entering the next phase of the NORF National Action Plan for Open Research, and to navigate this journey successfully, a comprehensive understanding of the current state of Open Access (OA) within the country is crucial. The National Open Access Monitor, Ireland (<https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/>) represents a significant leap forward in this regard. It serves as an innovative platform designed to promote and comprehend Open Access research and scholarly publishing within Ireland. This report, accompanying the Monitor, offers a thorough analysis of OA in Ireland, aiming to provide valuable insights and recommendations for the scholarly community.

Key Observations and Insights

Scholarly Production and Research Landscape Ireland demonstrates a strong commitment to academic rigor, with **78.7%** of its publications being **peer-reviewed**. The country boasts a dynamic research environment characterized by an increasing adoption of digital practices such as DOIs and repository usage. Fields of Science (FoS) analysis reveals that Natural Sciences, Clinical Medicine, and Health Sciences are prolific in peer-reviewed publications, while Engineering and Technology also show substantial scholarly activity. Social Sciences and Humanities, although not as voluminous, display rich diversity, indicating a need for more focused support in these areas. Journals remain the primary platform for hosting peer-reviewed publications, but there is a growing engagement with repositories, signifying an evolving landscape of research dissemination.

¹ The National Open Access Monitor, Ireland is delivered by OpenAIRE as part of the National Open Access Monitor Project, managed by the Irish Research eLibrary (IReL) at Maynooth University. The project has received funding from Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the Open Research Fund Call.

Commented [CF1]: Overall comment: report focuses on all time e.g. of ALL peer-reviewed publications since 2007, 38.6% are OA with license. This doesn't help the reader understand the current state of OA in Ireland. This also won't help us track improvements (as we'll never improve the e.g. 2007 data) so if we make great improvements next year, the issues with the 2007-2019 data will still make it look like there are issues overall. The ORCID data throughout is a useful example, the overall figure of 55% is used on page 77, but it's stated on page 44 that it was 71.7 in 2021.

Request insertion of more conclusions and summary statements throughout which emphasize how Ireland is doing now in achieving 100% open access and all aspects of open scholarship (or as close to "now" as OpenAIRE can determine).

Commented [GU2R1]: No, the report does not limit to 2007. It is the publications of all time, the timelines are shown for specific publication years so as to be more legible.

However, it is possible to refer to the rate of OA for publications of later years.

Commented [CF3R1]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU4]: Due to differing scholarly publishing practices. It's not that they are doing less research as this sentence suggests, and might be perceived poorly by AHSS scholars.

Commented [CF5R4]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU6R4]: The sentence will be clarified to explain that it's related to publication practices, was not meant as a comment on research output.

Open Access and Licensing Approximately **38.6%** of Irish peer-reviewed publications are available as **OA with a license**, aligning with the Budapest Open Access Initiative's definition. However, **17.6%** are **OA without a license**, and a significant portion (**26.3%**) remains Closed Access. This distribution underscores the need for more widespread adoption of OA practices. While there is a progressive shift towards OA with licenses, the persistence of Closed Access publications indicates ongoing challenges in transitioning away from traditional publishing models. Furthermore, discrepancies in licensing practices across different types of publications highlight systemic issues within the publishing industry that demand attention.

Commented [CF7]: Some readers may not understand the impact of this. At a minimum, propose updating this to "open without a license, which does not align with the BOAI definition of open access". Also scope to expand on why a license is important here.

Commented [GU8R7]: Will do.

OA Routes and Publishing Models Publisher-mediated OA, comprising Gold and Hybrid OA with **86,908** of all licensed OA publications (**67.3%**), predominates over repository-mediated OA in Ireland. This underscores the substantial influence of publishers in shaping the country's OA landscape. There is a noticeable upward trend in Hybrid OA, potentially influenced by Transformative Agreements and Transformative Journals. FoS analysis indicates that Medical and Health Sciences lead in publisher-mediated OA, while Social Sciences and Humanities proportionately benefit more from Transformative Agreements and Journals.

Plan S Compliance and Transformative Agreements A majority (**79.5%**) of Plan S-compliant publications in Ireland fall under the category of Gold OA with Article Processing Charges (APCs). However, a notable portion (**9%**) is published under Transformative Agreements, signifying an embrace of transitional strategies towards full OA. Disparities in Plan S compliance across different FoS suggest the necessity for tailored approaches to OA compliance. Transformative Agreements are increasingly significant, particularly **in Social Sciences and Humanities**, indicating a strategic shift in these fields towards OA publishing models.

Article Processing Charges (APCs) The average APC per publication in Ireland stands at approximately **EUR 2,200**, with a noticeable **increase in APCs over time**. It is worth noting that data coverage on APCs is limited, which restricts the scope for comprehensive analysis. Variations in average APCs across FoS highlight distinct trends and financial dynamics in OA publishing, with Medical and Health Sciences incurring higher APCs.

Commented [GU9]: The number or cost?

Commented [GU10R9]: will update.

FAIR Principles and Metadata Completeness Analysis of licensing reveals a mix of restrictive and more open Creative Commons licenses, indicating a gradual shift towards open research practices. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) like DOIs exhibit **100%** coverage by construction in peer-reviewed publications, with an **increasing trend** in the use of multiple PIDs per publication, suggesting a diversifying digital ecosystem. The rising use of ORCID iDs reflects greater engagement in managing digital scholarly identity and highlights the importance of visibility and recognition in scholarly communication.

Commented [GU11]: Coming from an RDM background I've never heard the FAIR principles applied to publications.

Commented [CF12R11]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU13R11]: While these principles are indeed primarily associated with data, their core concepts are increasingly being extended to scholarly publications as well.

Overall Observations Ireland's scholarly landscape is actively adapting to new norms and expectations in OA. While some fields are advancing in licensed OA, others, particularly in **Humanities and Agricultural Sciences**, lag, often constrained by traditional publication models and data representation. The trends indicate a positive shift towards more open and transparent research practices. Still, the persistence of Closed Access (**20.1%**) publications and disparities in licensing practices call for continued efforts to foster a more open scholarly communication environment.

The rise of Hybrid OA, the sustained presence of Gold OA, and the growing importance of Transformative Agreements showcase a publishing sphere adjusting to evolving mandates and researcher needs. Monitoring these changes is essential to ensure that the benefits of OA are maximized for the entire scholarly community. The disparities across disciplines and the varied impact of Transformative Agreements highlight the need for nuanced and **field-specific strategies** to effectively transition to more open and accessible research models.

Main Data Challenges

Inconsistent metadata within Open Access monitoring presents a formidable challenge. The presence of inconsistencies across various metadata elements, including naming conventions and standardization, hinders the accurate identification of critical entities such as Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), publishers, journals, and licenses. These discrepancies result in a lack of standardized practices, ultimately affecting the accuracy and reliability of the data.

Complex license reporting adds to the complexity. This challenge has two facets: firstly, there is a significant gap in including licenses in metadata, a crucial element for categorizing publications as OA. Secondly, the intricate understanding of licensing nuances, especially in mapping various licenses and their degrees of openness, complicates the precise classification of publications.

Timeliness and indexing issues further complicate the data landscape. Delays in reporting, incomplete indexing of recent publications, and underutilization of ORCID iDs for authors hinder the comprehensive and accurate representation of research outputs and their impacts.

Access rights and version complexity pose additional hurdles. The dynamic nature of access rights, combined with challenges in distinguishing different publication versions, adds intricacy to metadata. This complexity makes it challenging to provide a clear view of publication statuses, impacting data accuracy.

Limited accessibility to full-text PDFs for a significant portion of OA peer-reviewed publications hinders researchers' ability to access and utilize scholarly content effectively. This constraint also limits the potential for advanced text mining and insights extraction.

In summary, these challenges collectively impede the accuracy, completeness, and reliability of OA monitoring data. Addressing these issues is critical to fostering a more robust scholarly communication environment and maximizing the benefits of Open Access.

Recommendations in Brief

In the pursuit of advancing OA in Ireland, the Monitor platform plays a crucial role. This report offers a comprehensive view, outlining direct and indirect improvement strategies, as well as long-term solutions and workflow recommendations, to enhance OA monitoring.

Direct Improvement Strategies emphasize leveraging existing tools and functionalities within the OpenAIRE ecosystem. These strategies are tailored to address challenges in metadata accuracy and completeness. By encouraging key stakeholders like policy makers, publishers, research funding and performing organizations (RFOs/RPOs), and researchers to adopt specific actions such as deduplication of organization names, joining OpenAIRE for data enrichment, and engaging with the Monitor dashboard, the goal is to enhance the overall quality and user experience of the Monitor. This approach not only refines data management but also encourages active participation and feedback from various stakeholders in the research community.

Indirect Improvement Strategies focus on elevating the overall quality of data harvested into OpenAIRE. These strategies are designed to address timely reporting, accurate metadata entry, and clear licensing, involving a collective effort from all stakeholders. Key recommendations include the development of policies for the registration and timely deposition of research outputs, implementation of consistent metadata standards across publications, and regular updating of publication records in institutional repositories. These actions are essential for ensuring the precision and comprehensiveness of data, thereby facilitating a more robust and reliable Open Access monitoring system.

The Long-Term Solutions and Workflow Recommendations shift the focus to sustainable improvements and future readiness. Focusing on sustainable data management, long-term data preservation, routine data quality audits, and comprehensive training and capacity building, these recommendations are crafted to ensure that the Open Access ecosystem is well-equipped to adapt, grow, and maintain high standards of data integrity.

and usefulness. Emphasis is placed on developing frameworks for iterative improvement in metadata standards, promoting global policy initiatives that align with the FAIR principles, and establishing collaborative platforms for metadata correction and enrichment.

By aligning these strategies closely with the challenges and gaps identified in the Data Evaluation, the report ensures a data-driven and targeted approach. This strategy addresses current needs and prepares for future challenges in OA monitoring and research data management, laying the groundwork for a more open, accessible, and efficient scholarly communication environment in Ireland.

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Abbreviations

APC	Article Processing Charge
CC	Creative Commons
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FoS	FoS
Graph	OpenAIRE Graph
IReL	The consortium of Irish research libraries
Monitor	National Open Access Monitor, Ireland
MU	Maynooth University
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NORF	National Open Research Forum
OA	Open Access
OFR	Open Funder Registry
OS	Open Science
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFI	Science Foundation Ireland
TA	Transformative Agreement
VoR	Version of Record
ROR	Research Organization Registry
ISNI	International Standard Name Identifier
GRID	Global Research Identifier Database

Commented [CF14]: "Fields of Science"?

Commented [GU15R14]: Yes, we missed it.

Commented [GU16]: Should ML (Machine Learning) also be included here?

Commented [GU17]: I think it's worth mentioning that this term is interchangeable with Open Research, as NORF is the Open Research forum.

Commented [GU18]: These bottom 3 are not in alphabetical order.

Glossary

TERM	DEFINITION
ARTICLE PROCESSING CHARGE (APC)	The fee charged by publishers in order to publish a research publication in an open access journal. These charges are meant to cover the costs of publication and ensure the work is freely accessible to all.
RESEARCH OUTPUTS/PRODUCTS	The four different types of research products in the OpenAIRE Graph: <u>Publications</u> , <u>Research data</u> , <u>Research software</u> , <u>Other research products</u> .
OPEN ACCESS	We uses the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access": "By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself." ²
TRANSFORMATIVE AGREEMENTS	Transformative Agreements are those contracts negotiated between institutions (libraries, national and regional consortia) and publishers that transform the business model underlying scholarly journal publishing, moving from one based on toll access (subscription) to one in which publishers are remunerated a fair price for their Open Access publishing services ³ .
JOURNAL BUSINESS MODELS	
OA (GOLD)	A journal that publishes only in OA.
DIAMOND OA	An OA (Gold) journal that does not charge article processing charges (APCs).
SUBSCRIPTION	A journal that charges for access to its articles.
HYBRID	A subscription journal where some of its articles are open access.

Commented [CF19]: The definition for "publications" is at the end of page 20/beginning of page 21, but as it's used throughout, a definition here would be helpful to be clear on what is meant by "publications".

² <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/>

³ <https://www.coalition-s.org/Transformative-journals-faq/>

TRANSFORMATIVE

A Transformative Journal is a subscription/hybrid journal that is actively committed to transitioning to a fully Open Access journal. In addition, a Transformative Journal must gradually increase the share of Open Access content; and offset subscription income from payments for publishing services (to avoid double payments).⁴

ROUTES TO OPEN ACCESS

GREEN WITH LICENCE

Green articles are published in toll-access journals, but archived in an OA archive, or "repository". These repositories may be discipline-specific (like ArXiv) or institutional repositories operated by universities or other institutions. Green articles may be published versions or preprints, and must be accompanied by a specified licence that outlines how the material can be used, shared, and distributed.

HYBRID OA

Hybrid articles are free to read at the time of publication, with an open licence. These are usually published in exchange for an article processing charge, or APC.

GOLD OA

Gold articles have all the same characteristics as Hybrid articles, but are published in all-Open Access journals, which are in turn called "Gold journals", or just "OA journals".

UNREALISED OA

BRONZE

Bronze articles are free to read on the publisher's website, without a licence that grants any other rights. There may be a delay between publication and availability to read, and often articles can be removed unilaterally by the publisher.

GREEN WITHOUT LICENCE

Green articles deposited in a repository without any licence specified.

ACCESSIBILITY - INTEROPERABILITY

ACCESSIBLE

A publication is accessible if the text file can be fetched via a valid URL in its metadata.⁵

INTEROPERABLE

A publication is considered interoperable if its full-text is in a machine-readable format, allowing machines to process and understand the content⁶.

Commented [CF20]: Propose that "Closed" would also be unrealised OA, and could be included here as a definition, as referred to on page 33.

Commented [GU21R20]: ok

⁴<https://www.coalition-s.org/Transformative-journals-faq/>

⁵ I.e., if a publication does not include a valid URL, we cannot assess accessibility.

⁶ This is not the only prerequisite for interoperability but we adopt this definition here for exposition.

1 Introduction

As Ireland embarks on the next phase of the NORF National Action Plan for Open Research, it is crucial to understand the current state of Open Access (OA) in the country. The National Open Access Monitor, Ireland, represents a significant step in this direction. It marks an advancement in understanding and promoting Open Access research and scholarly publishing within Ireland. This report is an integral companion to the Monitor, a dynamic and innovative platform designed to guide Ireland's scholarly output towards 100% Open Access. Currently in its pilot phase until June 2024, the Monitor is accessible at <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/>.

This report aims to establish a comprehensive baseline analysis of OA in Ireland, offering both a holistic and domain-specific perspective. It evaluates current Irish OA publishing practices and uptake, highlights challenges, and proposes solutions.

Open Access monitoring is a pivotal tool in decision-making, policy formulation, and the advancement of scholarly communication. By providing clear insights into the state of OA, this monitoring effort enables stakeholders to make informed decisions, strategize effectively, and foster a more open and collaborative research environment. It is a key driver in the transformation towards a more transparent, accessible, and equitable scholarly landscape.

The analysis of OA in Ireland, presented in Section 2, provides a detailed view of the current state and progression of scholarly communication, focusing on the Irish scholarly production, various Open and FAIR aspects and Plan S compliance, APCs and Transformative Agreements. The section concludes by bringing together key observations and insights from our analysis, underscoring both the achievements and the challenges that need to be addressed to further advance OA in Ireland.

Section 4 outlines the methodological steps undertaken in the analysis. This transparent approach assures the integrity and reliability of our findings and paves the way for the data evaluation and challenges presented in Section 4. These findings are crucial for understanding the current landscape of data quality and integrity, which are fundamental in shaping effective Open Access monitoring and policy development.

Finally, Section 5 presents a series of strategies and recommendations aimed at enhancing OA monitoring in Ireland. Our approach spans three interconnected tiers of improvement, encompassing direct improvement strategies for the Monitor, indirect

improvement strategies for data enhancement, and forward-looking strategies for long-term OA monitoring enhancements.

This report, therefore, stands as a foundational step in Ireland's journey towards a fully open scholarly environment, setting the stage for ongoing analysis, policy development, and strategic action in Open Access publishing.

1.1 Methodological Foundations for the National Open Access Monitor and Report

In the development of both the National Open Access Monitor, Ireland, and this accompanying report, we have employed a methodological framework that is deeply rooted in the principles of Open Science. This approach is designed to provide thorough, accurate, and user-focused insights into Ireland's Open Access landscape. Central to our methodology is the OpenAIRE Graph (<https://graph.openaire.eu/>), which serves as the foundational data resource⁷. Our methodological principles encompass the following core areas.

Openness and Transparency: Our methods are grounded in transparency, using only publicly available data. We strictly adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles and international standards. This commitment ensures that our findings are not only trustworthy and replicable but also readily accessible for public scrutiny and engagement.

Comprehensive Coverage and Precision: By harnessing the extensive data capabilities of the OpenAIRE Graph and collaborating closely with various stakeholders, our aim is to capture the most complete and nuanced picture of OA in Ireland. This involves integrating data from a wide array of sources, ensuring that our indicators are both accurate and rich in detail.

Readiness and Timeliness: Our framework is built upon established open databases and proven technologies in natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML). These tools are integrated into OpenAIRE's operational workflows, enabling us to provide timely and relevant results that are in step with the latest developments in the field.

⁷ See Section 3 for details.

Engagement and Inclusivity: At the core of our methodology is a commitment to serve a diverse array of users, from individual researchers to policy makers. We focus on creating an intuitive, user-friendly experience, underpinned by clear communication and an openness to feedback. This approach ensures that our platform is not only informative but also engaging and responsive to the varied needs of all stakeholders in the research community.

These guiding principles are the bedrock of our work, shaping both the National Open Access Monitor and this Report. They ensure that our efforts are not only methodologically robust and comprehensive but also aligned with the evolving needs and expectations of Ireland's research community.

2 Baseline Analysis

In this chapter, we conduct a baseline analysis of Open Access (OA) in Ireland, examining the various facets that shape its landscape. Our exploration begins with an analysis of scholarly production, where we gauge the volume and trends of peer-reviewed publications. We segment this data by year, scientific field, and publication types, providing insights into the growth and diversification of scholarly outputs.

We proceed to explore the different OA pathways, specifically contrasting repository-mediated and publisher-mediated OA. This examination includes assessing both immediate and embargoed OA, as well as instances of unrealized OA. This part of our analysis seeks to unravel the complexities in the distribution and evolution of these OA models across the Irish academic landscape, elucidating how these approaches are adopted and their trajectories over time and various disciplines.

The chapter also delves into compliance with the FAIR principles. We evaluate the prevalence of essential elements such as licences, abstracts, and ORCID IDs in publications. This assessment aims to reveal the degree to which Irish research aligns with these international standards, pinpointing areas of robust compliance and potential opportunities for enhancement.

We then turn our focus to Plan S compliance trends among Irish OA publications and the financial aspects of OA publishing in Ireland, with a specific focus on Article Processing Charges (APCs) and the impact of Transformative Agreements. This section aims to shed light on the economic dynamics underpinning OA publishing practices.

The chapter concludes with a synthesis of our key findings, integrating the various analytical threads to present a comprehensive overview of the current state of OA in Ireland.

2.1 Scholarly Production

This section provides a foundational exploration of Ireland's scientific production, offering essential context for our analysis. By scrutinizing the distribution of publications across time, disciplines, and types, we gain a comprehensive understanding of the country's research landscape. This analysis serves as a crucial backdrop for a more in-depth investigation into Open Access (OA) within the Irish scholarly community.

Table 1: Outline of overall production of Irish publications

# Irish publications	418,322
# and % of Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications	329,308 (78.7%)

Among the **418,322** total Irish publications, a significant **329,308 (78.7%)** are peer-reviewed, underscoring the high academic and scientific rigor of Irish research output. This proportion points to a strong emphasis on quality in scholarly work.

The analysis of Irish publications reveals a steadily rising trend in peer-reviewed output over the years. Starting at **8,714** in 2007 and peaking at **22,083** in 2020, this upward trend signifies a burgeoning and dynamic research environment in Ireland and an increased adoption of digital practices such as the use of DOIs and digital repositories, which are critical for peer-reviewed recognition. The drop in 2022 likely results from delays in indexing and reporting, illustrating the ebb and flow typical in publication data⁸.

Commented [CF22]: Propose consistent use of "scholarly" here, in line with section heading, rather than "scientific".

Commented [GU23R22]: ok

Commented [GU24]: What time period does this cover?

Commented [GU25R24]: Everything that is in the OpenAIRE graph without any limit. We can check the earlier date available, but that does not mean there aren't earlier publications without a YEAR present.

Commented [GU26]: worth pointing to the page in the report where the methodology of what constitutes an 'Irish publication' is explained.

⁸ For a discussion of data evaluation see Section 4.

Figure 1: Irish Publications Trends

To provide a more detailed understanding of Ireland's research landscape, we next examine the distribution of publications across various **Fields of Science (FoS)**, both at the broader level 1 and the more specific level 2 categories⁹. This granular view reveals leading disciplines in peer-reviewed publications, and those at the forefront of digital research reporting. The Natural Sciences, particularly physical and chemical sciences, along with clinical medicine and health sciences, emerge as prolific areas.

Engineering and technology disciplines also stand out, reflecting their growing relevance in contemporary research. In contrast, Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences, though smaller in scale, show focused research efforts in specialized areas, indicating niche expertise within these fields.

The Social Sciences and humanities, while not as voluminous as fields like engineering, display a rich diversity of research. This could be due to differences in publication practices across disciplines. This diversity is vital for a balanced research landscape but also **highlights areas needing more focus or resources**.

⁹ See Section 3.4 for a description of OpenAIRE's FoS classification system. We note that 74.7% of all peer-reviewed publications have been classified to FoS classes. The rest has insufficient metadata to be classified to an FoS class.

Commented [GU27]: There is a focus here on the volume of publications, noting differences across different disciplines, do these differences align with what is seen on an international level? I would guess this is not unique to Ireland.

Commented [GU28R27]: We can examine cross-country trends if this is needed.

Commented [CF29R27]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [CF30]: I'm not clear in the conclusion here. It reads as though the diversity highlights a need for more focus/resources? Is that intended?

Commented [GU31R30]: the diversity in output could be because of publications practices or it could be because certain areas are underfunded or both

Commented [CF32R30]: For further discussion at the meeting

Figure 2: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (levels 1 & 2)

An examination of the types of Irish peer-reviewed publications reveals a clear dominance of articles, which constitute **82.8%** of the total. This is followed by other literature types (**11.1%**) and conference objects (**10.5%**), with book chapters and preprints also contributing to the scholarly mix¹⁰.

Table 2: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Type (top 7)

	# Irish peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish peer-reviewed publications
Article	272,536	82.8%

¹⁰ In the OpenAIRE Graph, numerous publications appear in multiple instances due to their life cycle and metadata variations. As a result, a single publication might be represented both as an article and as a pre-print, reflecting its different stages of publication. This dual representation can also arise from discrepancies or inaccuracies in metadata reporting.

Other literature type	36,521	11.1%
Conference object	34,368	10.5%
Part of book or chapter of book	22,172	6.7%
Preprint	12,097	3.7%
Thesis	6,156	1.9%
Book	1,152	0.3%

Journals are the primary data source for peer-reviewed publications, followed by **Publication and Institutional Repositories**. This distribution highlights the continued primacy of journals in academic publishing and a growing engagement with repositories as complementary research dissemination platforms.

Commented [CF33]: It would be helpful to state what a "Publication Repository" is

Figure 3: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Data Source Type

Figure 4: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by SDGs

We then shift our focus to the thematic impact of Irish research in relation to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This analysis shows how Irish research output addresses global challenges, with significant emphasis on health and environmental issues. The prominence of SDGs like "Good Health," "Climate Action," and "Life Underwater" in Irish publications aligns with global priorities and underscores the societal relevance of Ireland's research endeavours¹¹.

Commented [CF34]: "Clean energy" is higher than "Life underwater" and is perhaps worth mentioning too here.

In summary, the analysis of scholarly production sets the stage for understanding the nuances of OA publishing in Ireland. It highlights the strengths and focuses of various research disciplines and sheds light on the evolving landscape of research dissemination, characterized by a blend of traditional and emerging platforms.

¹¹ ~30% of Irish PR publications have been classified to an SDG. The rest have not been classified to an SDG either due to lack of relevance or lack of good quality metadata.

2.2 Open & FAIR

In this section, we delve into a set of essential indicators that illuminate the openness and FAIRness of publications within Ireland's scholarly landscape. This analysis forms a crucial foundation for understanding the current state of OA in Ireland and identifying areas where improvements and interventions may be necessary.

2.2.1 Access Rights

Here, we delve deeper into the nature of access rights associated with Irish peer-reviewed publications, a crucial factor in understanding the OA landscape in Ireland. Our analysis is guided by the Budapest Open Access Initiative's definition, which considers only those publications with an associated licence as truly 'open access'. This distinction is vital for the assessment and the overall objectives of the Monitor.

Table 3: Number and Share of Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights

Access Rights	# Irish peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish peer-reviewed publications
Open Access w/ Licence	127,109	38.6%
Open Access w/o Licence	57,899	17.6%
Embargo	84	0.03%
Restricted	1488	0.4%
Closed Access	86,516	26.3%
Not Available	56,212	17.07%

Examining the access rights data, we find that **38.6%** of Irish peer-reviewed publications are OA with a licence. This is a significant proportion, but there is room for improvement, especially considering that **17.6%** are Open Access without a licence. These unlicensed publications, while accessible, lack the formal licensing that defines full openness and reusability under the Budapest standard. Notably, **Closed Access** publications still constitute **26.3%** of the total, indicating some persistence of traditional publishing models. The relatively high number of **17.07%** of peer-reviewed publications without any access rights present in their metadata requires further analysis and will be examined in the data evaluation section.

When we break down these access rights by data source types, the reliance on different platforms for disseminating research becomes evident.

- Journals, a primary data source, host a significant number of both licenced and unlicensed Open Access publications. However, the relatively higher number of

Commented [GU35]: How do you disambiguate closed access publications which have separately been made open via Green OA and those that have not been made open at all?

Commented [GU36R35]: This tables shows the best available access rights for a publication, therefore if Closed and Green OA, it would show up as Open Access here, we will explain it in the text.

Closed Access publications in journals suggests traditional models still dominate this space.

- Publication and Institutional Repositories not surprisingly show a strong inclination towards hosting Open Access content, with a considerable number of publications available with licences.
- Thematic Repositories and Publication Repository Aggregators also contribute to the Open Access ecosystem, albeit with lower overall numbers.

Figure 5: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights by Data Source Type

This analysis underscores the progress made towards achieving Open Access in Ireland, particularly in institutional and thematic repositories. It also highlights the ongoing challenges in fully transitioning to Open Access, especially within journal publishing. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping future strategies and policies aimed at enhancing the openness and fairness of scholarly communication in Ireland.

To delve deeper into this trend, the following chart provides a chronological breakdown. Over the years, there has been a clear trend towards increasing Open Access with licencing. Starting from a modest base in 2007, there has been a significant year-on-year rise, peaking in recent years. This growth trajectory underscores a progressive shift towards more open and transparent research practices in Ireland. Open Access without licencing

is decreasing as a share of total Open Access indicating improvement in licensing practices over the years.

The trend in Closed Access publications is decreasing slightly over time in absolute and relative terms while still represent a notable portion of the total output. This may be due to Open Science practices being adopted at varying rates by different Fields of Science.

Commented [CF37]: typo: representing

Figure 6: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights over time

A deeper analysis of access rights across different Fields of Science (FoS) at both the broad Level 1 and the more detailed Level 2 categories reveals insightful trends in Ireland's OA landscape.

Medical and Health Sciences, with the largest scholarly output, lead in OA with licenced publications. Together with Natural Sciences and engineering, these fields see over half of their peer-reviewed publications as OA. Social sciences slightly trail in this regard. In contrast, agricultural, veterinary sciences, and humanities exhibit a higher Closed vs. Open Access ratio, suggesting a slower transition from traditional publishing models. This

Commented [GU38]: Are certain fields more prolific because of scholarly publishing practices in those fields or because we have a higher proportion of researchers in these fields?

Commented [GU39R38]: I don't think we can say for sure.

view is nuanced by potential data underrepresentation, which may affect our understanding of their OA progression.

Figure 7: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights by FoS (level 1)

Drilling down to FoS level 2, we observe that environmental engineering stands out within the engineering sector, likely due to its interdisciplinary connections. In Social Sciences, disciplines like education, law, and political science show a smaller Open Access footprint, indicating diverse adoption rates of Open Science practices within the field.

Figure 8: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights by FoS (level 2)

In terms of publication types, articles demonstrate the highest adoption of OA with a licence and the most favourable ratio of licenced to unlicensed OA. Conversely, conference materials, books, and book chapters lag in licensing practices. Particularly, book sections or chapters show a Closed Access rate nearing **40%**, representing around **8,000** publications, indicating a considerable reliance on traditional access models for these types of works.

Table 4: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights by Publication Type

	% OA with licence	% OA w/o licence	% Closed Access
Article	44.6%	13.8%	27.6%
Conference object	20.5%	32.3%	8%
Part of book or chapter of book	14.9%	16.8%	39.9%
Book	15.9%	38.4%	9.8%

As we have examined the various data sources, temporal changes, and disciplinary fields, the push towards Open Access is multifaceted and unevenly distributed across different sectors of the scholarly landscape. While some fields, such as Medical and Health Sciences, are leading the way in licenced Open Access, others, especially in the humanities and agricultural sciences, are lagging, potentially hampered by traditional publication models and a lack of representation in digital repositories.

The trends over time indicate a positive shift towards more open and transparent research practices, with Open Access with licence steadily increasing. However, the persistence of Closed Access publications—although slightly decreasing—highlights the ongoing challenge of transitioning to Open Access models.

The discrepancies observed in licensing practices across different types of publications, with articles faring better than conference outputs and book chapters, potentially point to systemic issues within the publishing industry that need addressing to foster a more open scholarly communication environment.

2.2.2 Open Access Routes

Repository-mediated vs publisher mediated OA

This section on OA routes provides a critical perspective on how Irish peer-reviewed publications with licences are made available. The distinction between repository-mediated OA (Green OA with a licence) and publisher-mediated OA, which includes both Gold and Hybrid OA, is significant in understanding the dynamics of OA dissemination. The first thing to note is that if Green OA was considered without a consideration about the licence this section would provide a very different view of repository uptake and practices in Ireland. We try to capture some of this in the next section on “Unrealised OA.”

From the data, we observe that publisher-mediated OA is the predominant route, with Gold OA accounting for **38.4%** and Hybrid OA making up **30%** of the total licenced OA publications. In comparison, repository-mediated OA represents a smaller share at **6.7%**. This suggests that while repositories play an essential role in OA dissemination, publishers currently have a more significant impact on the OA landscape in Ireland.

Table 5: Repository Mediated vs Publisher Mediated OA Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications

OA route	# Irish OA licenced peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish OA licenced peer-reviewed publications
Repository mediated OA (Green OA w/ licence)	8,483	6.7%

Publisher mediated OA (Gold OA)	48,795	38.4%
Publisher mediated OA (Hybrid OA)	38,113	30% ¹²

Trend data from 2007 to 2022 reveals nuanced shifts in OA publishing routes. Growth is seen across all categories, with repository-mediated OA showing an encouraging rise in its proportion of total OA publications with a licence. This indicates a strengthened role for repositories in the OA landscape. However, the share of publications represented in both repository and publisher categories (the blue boxes in the figure below) has not seen a consistent increase, suggesting that repositories may be underutilized for OA publications. This could point to a missed opportunity for maximizing the reach and impact of scholarly work through dual availability in both repositories and through publishers.

Figure 9: Repository-mediated vs Publisher-mediated Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications Over Time

Upon examining the data by FoS, we find that Medical and Health Sciences lead the way in publisher-mediated OA, mirroring global trends that emphasize the immediate access

¹² The 24.9% of OA PR publications with licence missing from the table can neither be attributed to a journal or a repository and is therefore not in the categories above.

to medical research findings. Natural sciences, along with Engineering and Technology, also predominantly utilize publisher-mediated channels for OA, which may be influenced by the funding and publishing cultures inherent to these fields.

Agricultural and veterinary sciences, alongside Social Sciences, and humanities, present a more equitable distribution between publisher-mediated and repository-mediated OA. This suggests a diversification in OA practices within these fields. Notably, the humanities show the highest engagement with repository-mediated OA.

Figure 10: Repository-mediated vs Publisher-mediated OA Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (level 1)

Lastly, we observe a discernible trend in the distribution of Gold versus Hybrid OA publications. The data indicates a steady increase in the proportion of Hybrid OA, suggesting a shift in journal policies from traditional subscription models to hybrid models. This transition, potentially driven by Transformative Journals or agreements, becomes particularly noticeable from 2020 onwards. By 2021 and 2022, the shares of Gold and Hybrid OA publications are nearly identical, reflecting a significant change in the publishing landscape.

This trend towards Hybrid OA may be a response to evolving OA policies and the growing adoption of Plan S principles. The subsequent section on Plan S and Transformative

Agreements will delve deeper into this aspect, offering a clearer understanding of the forces shaping these trends.

Figure 11: Gold OA vs Hybrid OA vs Green OA with Licence over Time

Table 6: Gold OA vs Hybrid OA vs Green OA with Licence over Time

Year	Green OA w/ Licence	Gold OA	Hybrid OA
2007	45	498	421
2008	55	676	501
2009	56	906	681
2010	87	1105	820
2011	116	1340	991
2012	142	1612	1087
2013	239	1874	1095
2014	242	2061	1360
2015	350	2807	1549
2016	589	3089	1917

2017	783	3597	1938
2018	973	3888	2734
2019	1177	4673	3206
2020	1233	5761	4026
2021	1100	5527	5382
2022	831	3987	4005

In summary, the shifting trends in OA publishing in Ireland reflect a landscape that is actively adapting to new norms. The rise of Hybrid OA, complemented by the steady prevalence of Gold OA, showcases a publishing sphere that is adjusting to evolving mandates and the diverse requirements of researchers. It is essential to keep an eye on how these changes influence the accessibility and utilization of research, with a focus on fully leveraging the advantages of OA for the wider scholarly community.

2.2.3 Immediate vs Embargo Open Access

In our exploration of Open Access (OA) practices, we focus on the timing of access — whether publications are made immediately available (immediate OA) or are initially embargoed. We note the following.

- Gold and Hybrid OA publications are available immediately, providing instant access upon publication.
- Green OA with a licence can also be immediate OA, but this depends on whether the article is submitted to a repository at the time of its publication and in its version of record (VoR). Unfortunately, these specific metadata elements (submission time and version type) are not regularly exposed by repositories, making it challenging to track this trend accurately.
- Embargoed OA articles present a unique challenge in tracking trends. Typically, they are only marked as 'embargoed' in the metadata until the embargo period expires. This categorization means that understanding the patterns of embargoed publications over time is complex, especially considering the currently low number of publications (only **83**) tagged explicitly as 'embargoed'.

These observations suggest a limitation in our ability to comprehensively assess the trends and variations between immediate and embargoed OA practices. The low tagging rate of embargoed articles hints at potential underreporting, which could skew the

Commented [CF40]: Request update in text and any impacted figures/tables/conclusions.

This statement is incorrect. Green OA with a license can also be an Authors Accepted Manuscript, submitted to a repository at the time of its publication in VOR form.

Whether it is AAM or VOR does not define whether it is green; nor does it define if it's immediate or embargo.

Commented [GU41R40]: To clarify, we include anything found OA with a licence in a repository as Green OA with licence.

In terms of its immediacy we would need deposit dates.

In terms of the versioning: if it is a pre-print would you still consider a pre-print deposited on the date of publication as satisfying immediate OA?

Pending answer to the above, we will go ahead and edit this text (it hasn't influenced anything else)

Commented [CF42R40]: For further discussion at the meeting

understanding of how often and effectively the embargoed route is being utilized in OA publishing¹³.

Table 7: Immediate vs. Embargo Irish OA Peer-Reviewed Publications

	OA route	# Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence	% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence
Immediate OA	Green OA with licence	8,483	6.7%
	Gold OA	48,795	38.4%
	Hybrid OA	38,113	30%
	Embargo OA	84	0.07%

2.2.4 Unrealised Open Access

Analysing unrealised Open Access (OA) is crucial as it uncovers the gaps between potential and actual open accessibility of scholarly outputs. Unrealised OA encompasses three types of peer-reviewed publications:

1. **Closed Access publications:** Represent traditional publishing models, indicating areas where OA is not yet realized.
2. **Green Publications without a licence:** Fail the Budapest OA Initiative's definition of OA due to the absence of a licence, reflecting a gap in metadata practices.
3. **Bronze publications:** These are accessible but unlicensed, again not meeting the full criteria for OA.

The large volume of Green publications without a licence (**72,042**) compared to those with a licence (**8,483**) suggests significant community practices impacting repository uptake. If licensing discrepancies are addressed, the landscape of repository vs. publisher-mediated OA discussed in Section 2.2.2 might appear considerably different. Ensuring automatic licensing in repositories, if not already in practice, could be a Transformative step.

Table 8: Unrealised OA in Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications

Commented [CF43]: The capitalisation of Transformative infers "Transformative Agreement" or "Transformative Journal", was this deliberate?

Commented [GU44R43]: No, typo.

¹³ For more details on metadata coverage and quality, see Section 4.

Unrealised OA	# Irish peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish peer-reviewed publications
Closed Access	86,516	26.3%
Green without Licence	72,042	21.9%
Bronze	122,397	37.2%

Trend analysis shows a steady increase in Bronze and Green publications without a licence, indicating a growing but unrealized potential for OA. Closed Access publications, on the other hand, have shown a plateauing trend.

Figure 12: Unrealised OA Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications Over Time

Turning to specific disciplines, Humanities and the Arts, along with Social Sciences, exhibit a high ratio of Bronze to Green OA without licence, led by a significant number of Bronze publications. This prevalence might indicate a preference for accessible but unlicensed forms of publishing in these fields, perhaps due to specific disciplinary norms or publishing agreements.

The Medical and Health Sciences, despite their high research output, also have substantial publications in Closed Access, Green without Licence, and Bronze categories. This suggests the potential for significant shifts towards more openness. The lower ratio of Closed Access to Green without licence plus Bronze in these sciences indicates their closer alignment with OA principles, pending better licensing.

In FoS level 2, physical sciences, chemical sciences, and various engineering fields have a notable presence in Bronze OA. This pattern might be indicative of discipline-specific publishing cultures that lean towards OA but with limitations on openness or accessibility.

Figure 13: Unrealised Open Access Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (level 1)

Figure 14: Unrealised Open Access Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (level 2)

Encouraging proper licensing in Green OA, can greatly enhance the accessibility and usability of these publications. While Bronze OA does not necessarily signify bad practices, it reflects a semi-open state that could benefit from more explicit licensing to fully align with OA standards.

Given the disparities across disciplines, a tailored approach to OA policy and advocacy seems more effective than a universal strategy. Understanding the unique needs and characteristics of each field is key to successfully transitioning them towards more open and accessible research models.

2.2.5 FAIR

The FAIR principles, which stand for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, guide the management and sharing of digital assets in a way that makes them more useful and valuable to a wide range of users. Each principle correlates with specific aspects of the analysis we present below.

Findable

- **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs):** PIDs, such as DOIs, are crucial for making data findable. They provide unique and persistent references to digital objects, making it easier for both humans and machines to locate the associated data or publications.
- **Abstracts:** The presence of abstracts enhances the findability of research outputs. Abstracts provide a concise summary of the content, aiding in the discovery process during searches.

Commented [GU45]: Other metadata?

Accessible

- **Licences:** The type of licence assigned to a publication affects its accessibility. Open licences like Creative Commons (CC) facilitate broader access by defining clear usage rights. This clarity helps users understand how they can legally access and use the data.
- **Accessibility of full-text:** This refers to the ability of users to retrieve the full text of a publication in a machine-readable format.

Interoperable

- **Use of PIDs:** Beyond findability, PIDs also contribute to interoperability. They help link data across different platforms and databases, facilitating the integration of data for comprehensive analysis and use.
- **File format of full-text:** This refers to the machine-readability of the full-text of the publication.

Reusable

- **Licences:** Again, licences play a critical role in the reusability of data. Licences that clearly articulate usage rights and restrictions enable users to understand how they can reuse and repurpose data.
- **ORCID IDs:** Associating ORCID IDs [and other PIDs such as ROARs and RAIDs](#) with publications increases their reusability. These IDs unambiguously link researchers to their work, aiding in attribution and ensuring that the right contributors get credit for their work.

Each of these elements contributes to making research outputs more FAIR - enhancing their value, ensuring their long-term utility, and promoting more efficient and effective science¹⁴.

LICENCES

Figure 15: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by Licence

The type of licence a publication carries significantly influences its reuse and distribution. Here, we focus on the prevalence and variety of licences used, which offer insights into how accessible and reusable these publications are under the FAIR [frameworkPrinciples](#).

A substantial portion of publications is under **restrictive licences** from major publishers like Elsevier TDM (**46,912 peer-reviewed publications**), Wiley Online Library User Agreement (**26,241**), and Springer TDM (**22,040**). These licences often limit the use of the content,

Commented [GU46]: Are these licences considered fully open access under the Budapest defn?

¹⁴ Overall metadata completeness of publications and other research products can be achieved by following the latest version of the OpenAIRE Guidelines (<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>). Institutional data sources registered in OpenAIRE PROVIDE (<https://provide.openaire.eu/>) can use the Metadata Validator (<https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.validator>) to directly measure the metadata completeness of their institutional outputs.

especially regarding text and data mining (TDM), which can restrict the full exploitation of these publications for advanced research purposes¹⁵.

In contrast, Creative Commons (CC) licences, which are more open and flexible, appear significantly. CC BY (**45,241**) is the most prevalent, followed by CC BY NC ND (**18,359**) and CC BY NC (**7,128**). The presence of these licences indicates a commitment to Open Science, enhancing the accessibility and reusability of research outputs¹⁶.

Table 9: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with and without a CC licence

	# Irish peer-reviewed publications	% of Irish peer-reviewed publications
with CC licence	74,061	22.5%
without CC licence	255,247	77.5%

The licensing landscape in Irish scholarly publications thus presents a mixed picture. While restrictive licences from publishers are still common, the increasing adoption of CC licences points to a gradual shift towards more open and transparent research practices. Understanding these licensing trends is crucial in shaping future strategies and policies aimed at promoting more open and FAIR-compliant research outputs.

¹⁵ The licenses from major publishers like Elsevier, Wiley, and Springer, as well as those from other entities listed, generally tend to be more restrictive compared to Creative Commons licenses. They often limit the use for text and data mining (TDM) and restrict commercial use and redistribution. They also vary significantly in permissiveness.

¹⁶ Other licences can be considered Open upon examination of the legal agreement. Those identified by Unpaywall as Open were not discussed herein as they are not significantly present in the Monitor dataset <https://support.unpaywall.org/support/solutions/articles/44002063718-what-is-an-oa-license->.

Figure 16: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with a CC Licence over Time

In FoS level 1 categories, we note that the variations across CC licensing uptake are not as high as for other metadata elements, they are all around **20%**, with Medical and Health Sciences leading at **24.9%** and Humanities and the Arts lagging behind with **14.2%**. This is not as surprising given the higher share of Closed Access publications in the latter.

Figure 17: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with a CC Licence by FoS (level 1)

In terms of the types of peer-reviewed publications, preprints show the highest proportion of CC licensing at **43.8%**. This high adoption rate aligns with the growing trend of early research dissemination and open peer review in the academic community. Articles, which form the bulk of scholarly output, have a significant but lower CC licensing rate at **26%**. Conference objects have a moderate CC licensing rate of **13.4%**. The nature of conference proceedings, often seen as preliminary findings or platforms for discussion, may contribute to this middling uptake. Encouraging more open licensing in conference materials can enhance the visibility and impact of these research outputs. Books and book chapters show the lowest levels of CC licensing, with books at **10%** and parts of books or chapters of books at just **6.8%**. This lower rate may reflect the traditional publishing models more prevalent in book publishing, where open licensing is less common.

Commented [CF47]: this sentence structure infers that preprints are peer-reviewed publications, request revision.

Commented [GU48R47]: Yes of course.

Commented [GU49]: Although there is a growing movement towards OA books.

Figure 18: Irish Peer- Reviewed Publications with a CC Licence by Publication Type

Turning to data sources, Thematic Repositories lead the way with a remarkable **56.8%** of their peer-reviewed content under CC licences. This high percentage underscores the commitment of thematic repositories to OA principles, ensuring that research is widely available and legally reusable. Institutional Repositories, with a **35%** rate of CC licence availability, demonstrate a significant portion of content adhering to OA, with potential for growth. Increasing the adoption of CC licences in these repositories could have a broad impact on the openness of scholarly communication across various fields.

Figure 19: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with a CC Licence by Data Source Type

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS (PIDs)

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) play a crucial role in the Open Access landscape as they enable the stable, long-term identification and accessibility of digital objects like publications. Their significance lies in their ability to facilitate the discovery, citation, and interlinking of research outputs, thus enhancing the integrity and efficiency of scholarly communication.

In the context of Irish peer-reviewed publications, the universal presence of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)¹⁷ guarantees a **100%** coverage of PIDs. Further analysis of PID types reveals an interesting trend: alongside the use of DOIs, there is an increasing employment of other identifier systems. The rising use of Handle IDs, growing from **968** in 2007 to **3,984** in 2020, highlights their growing significance in complementing DOIs, especially in institutional repositories where they ensure persistent access to digital resources. Similarly, PubMed Central IDs and PubMed IDs have seen considerable growth, particularly in Medical and Health Sciences. This trend reflects the sector's movement towards more

- Commented [CF50]:** Query: is 100% met? Or is it that only research outputs with DOIs are within scope of this report?
- Commented [GU51R50]:** PR publications have DOIs therefore by construction PR publications have 100% coverage of PIDs.
- Commented [CF52R50]:** For further discussion at the meeting
- Commented [GU53R50]:** This was an error there are (~10K) publications do not have a PID, we will alter the analysis.

¹⁷ By construction, a DOI from Crossref must be present for a publication to be peer-reviewed. See Section 3.5.

digital and easily accessible platforms, enhancing research visibility and interoperability within these disciplines.

The fact that there is a decreasing share of publications with only DOIs and an increase in those with multiple PIDs indicates a diversifying PID landscape. This can be viewed positively, as it suggests a richer, more interconnected digital ecosystem where research outputs are more easily discoverable and linked across various platforms and databases. However, it also poses challenges in terms of managing and harmonizing these identifiers to avoid confusion and ensure seamless integration. Therefore, while the trend towards multiple PIDs per publication enhances the robustness and reach of scholarly communication, it also underscores the need for coherent PID management strategies to maximize their benefits in the OA environment.

Figure 20: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with a CC Licence by PID Type over Time

ORCID iDs

ORCID iDs are unique identifiers assigned to individual researchers, playing a crucial role in distinguishing their work amidst the ever-expanding volume of scholarly publications. They are vital for several reasons: they resolve issues of name ambiguity, ensure accurate

attribution of work, and facilitate the seamless linkage and tracking of an individual's research outputs across various platforms and affiliations over time.

An increasing trend in the use of ORCID iDs reflects a growing awareness and adoption of these identifiers among the research community. Starting from a usage rate of **51.6%** in publications from 2007, there has been a notable rise to **72.4%** in 2020, though with a slight dip to **71.7%** in 2021. This upward trend signifies a positive shift towards more streamlined and efficient scholarly communication.

Figure 21: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with an ORCID iD over Time

The increasing use of ORCID iDs indicates that researchers are becoming more proactive in managing their digital scholarly identity, ensuring that their contributions are accurately recognized and easily discoverable. This trend is beneficial for the researchers, as it enhances their visibility and credit for their work. For the research ecosystem, it facilitates better data management, tracking, and analysis of research outputs and collaborations.

The slight decline in 2021 might be a result of various factors, including changes in publishing practices or fluctuations in the adoption rate of new technologies and standards among researchers. Despite this minor setback, the overall upward trajectory

is a promising sign of the research community's commitment to embracing digital tools that enhance the integrity and effectiveness of scholarly communication.

ABSTRACT

The presence of an abstract in research metadata is extremely important as it provides a concise summary of the research work, allowing readers to quickly assess the relevance and scope of the publication. Abstracts serve as a critical tool for researchers and scholars, aiding in the efficient evaluation and selection of literature relevant to their field of study.

Our data indicates an extremely high presence of abstracts in the metadata, consistently above **90%** up until 2021. This high percentage is indicative of robust metadata practices, suggesting that most publications are accompanied by summaries that can facilitate academic search and discovery.

However, it is important to approach these figures with caution. The mere presence of an abstract does not guarantee its quality or usefulness. In some cases, metadata may contain substandard abstracts, where the content could range from being irrelevant (such as a title or an acknowledgment being mistakenly labelled as an abstract) to incoherent or gibberish text. Therefore, while the high availability of abstracts is a good sign, it is equally crucial to ensure the quality and relevance of these abstracts to truly enhance the value and accessibility of the scholarly work.

Figure 22: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with an Abstract over Time

ACCESSIBILITY & INTEROPERABILITY

Of the **185K** OA peer-reviewed publications in the Graph (with and without licence), **84K (45%)** have valid URLs in their metadata. Out of those **61K**, i.e. **33%** of all OA peer-reviewed publications) URLs link directly the PDF of the full text, rendering them accessible and interoperable¹⁸.

Table 10: Accessibility & Interoperability of Irish OA Peer-Reviewed Publications

% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publication with a valid URL in their metadata	45%
% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications that are ACCESSIBLE (full-text can be fetched from URL link)	33%
% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications that are INTEROPERABLE (full-text is in a machine readable format)	33%

¹⁸ Interoperability is determined by a variety of other factors besides machine readability but we use the term here for ease of exposition.

CONCLUDING FAIR ASPECTS

The examination of various FAIR aspects within Irish peer-reviewed publications has yielded the following insights.

In the domain of licensing, the analysis presents a complex landscape. A substantial portion of publications is governed by restrictive licenses, primarily from major publishers, which could potentially limit their full utilization for research purposes. However, the presence of Creative Commons (CC) licenses in a significant number of publications is a positive sign, indicating a shift towards more open and transparent research practices. The variation in CC licensing uptake across Fields of Science is not dramatic, but notable differences exist, particularly in disciplines like Medical and Health Sciences, which lead in CC licensing. This highlights the importance of promoting more open and FAIR-compliant research outputs across various scientific fields.

Regarding Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), the universal presence of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) in Irish peer-reviewed publications ensures **100%** coverage, enhancing their discoverability and accessibility. The diversifying landscape of PIDs, with increasing use of multiple identifiers per publication, points towards a more interconnected digital ecosystem. This trend, while beneficial for enhancing the robustness and reach of scholarly communication, also calls for coherent PID management strategies to maximize their benefits and ensure seamless integration.

The increasing use of ORCID iDs reflects a positive development, with researchers becoming more engaged in managing their digital scholarly identity. This trend enhances visibility and recognition of individual researchers' contributions, contributing to more streamlined and efficient scholarly communication.

The high presence of abstracts in research metadata, consistently above **90%**, facilitates academic search and discovery. However, the quality and relevance of these abstracts need scrutiny to ensure they genuinely contribute to the value and accessibility of scholarly works.

Lastly, only about **33%** of OA peer-reviewed publications have a valid link to their full-text PDF in their metadata, suggesting room for improvement in this aspect.

2.3 Plan S, APCs & Transformative Agreements

2.3.1 Plan S

Plan S¹⁹ stands at the forefront of a major shift in OA publishing, especially since its requirements became effective post-2020. This initiative, led by cOAlition S, is a pivotal force reshaping the dissemination of publicly funded scientific research. Its aim is to ensure the immediate and universal accessibility of research outputs, marking a new chapter in the narrative of scientific publishing.

Central to Plan S is the requirement that researchers funded by cOAlition S members must publish their research findings in OA journals or platforms. This includes the adoption of various compliant routes, such as publication in OA journals, deposition in recognized repositories, and engagement with Transformative Journals and agreements that progressively shift towards full OA.

A critical aspect of Plan S is its stance on transparency and accountability regarding publication fees. It endeavours to set a standard for fair and reasonable OA publication fees, confronting the traditional financial models that have been dominating scientific publishing. Furthermore, Plan S emphasizes the importance of licensing, particularly advocating for the use of the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC BY). This approach not only enhances the openness of research but also enables the wider reuse of scholarly works with appropriate attribution to the original authors.

Currently there is only one funder in Ireland that is a member of cOAlition S, Science Foundation Ireland.

Table 11: Irish Plan S Funders - Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)

Irish Plan S Funders: Science Foundation Ireland	16,675 PR Publications
---	-------------------------------

The timeline below is meant to capture the pre- and post-Plan S (2021 onwards) access rights for SFI. In this case there seems to be a steady increase in the share of OA licensed peer-reviewed publications and a decrease in the share of unrealised OA (OA without licence and Closed Access) rather than a sudden shift, potentially indicating preparation for Plan S compliance.

¹⁹ <https://www.coalition-s.org/>

Figure 23: Peer-Reviewed Publications by Access Rights for SFI (Plan S Funder)

Followingly, we explore Plan S compliance indicators, particularly focusing on the period 2021 onwards and publications published

- in Diamond OA journals
- under Transformative Agreements
- in Transformative Journals
- following the Gold OA route.

Commented [GU54]: What is meant by transformative journals?

These components, while not exhaustive of all Plan S requirements, provide insights into the evolving dynamics of OA publishing. They help us understand how different OA models and agreements are being adopted and integrated in line with Plan S principles.

Table 12: Plan S-Compliant Irish Peer-Reviewed publications

		# Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence post-2020	% of Irish OA peer-reviewed publications w/ licence post-2020 ²⁰
Z	In Diamond Journals	46	0.21%

²⁰ Covering 2021, 2022.

Under Transformative Agreements	1427	6.38%
In Transformative Journals	1749	7.81%
Gold OA with APCs	12,467	55.7%

Commented [CF55]: There are 5,482 articles and conference proceedings published hybrid + 730 articles published gold under IReL agreements since 2020:
https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapc-de/tree/master/data/transformative_agreements/IReL

(a) Does this figure mean that OpenAIRE was unable to determine the open licenses for 4,055 articles?
(b) has this OpenAPC data been used in this report and the Monitor?

Commented [GU56R55]: The OpenAPC data we had in OpenAIRE included 1821 articles (1427 of which were identified) - we investigated as soon as we saw your comment, the full dataset is being integrated as we speak and we will update the report too.

Commented [GU57]: Does the 'not Plan S compliant' category here include Green OA? This graph seems to suggest that publications which do not fall into the four OA categories presented are not Plan S compliant, which is not correct

Commented [CF58R57]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU59R57]: Were planning on changing the name, thank you.

Figure 24: Plan S-Compliant Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications over Time

A significant majority of Plan S compliant publications are those published in Gold OA journals with APCs, accounting for **55.7%** of all OA peer-reviewed publications with a licence. This reliance on APCs might be sustainable in fields with adequate funding but raises concerns about inclusivity, particularly in less well-funded disciplines. Publications under Transformative Agreements and in Transformative Journals, represent **6.38%** and **7.81%** respectively. These figures indicate an increasing uptake of transitional strategies towards full OA, aligning with the Plan S push for Transformative routes. The growth in publications under Transformative Agreements in 2021 suggests the growing implementation of these agreements, which are brokered by IReL in Ireland. However, the number of publications in Diamond Journals, which offer OA without APCs, is markedly low at just **0.21%**. This small figure suggests that despite their potential as a cost-effective OA route, Diamond Journals may be underutilized or under-supported. This points to a

potential area for policy intervention and increased advocacy to boost their visibility and viability in the OA landscape.

Figure 25: Plan S-Compliant Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (level 1)

The Plan S compliance data for FoS level 1 shows that Medical and Health Sciences are at the forefront of embracing Open Access (OA) initiatives, with a high percentage of publications in Gold OA with APCs, and a significant number under Transformative Agreements. Natural Sciences and Engineering and Technology also demonstrate strong engagement with OA models, especially publisher-mediated ones. It is notable that Social Sciences and Humanities are leveraging Transformative Agreements and journals more effectively relative to their total OA output. This could be indicative of a strategic shift in these fields towards OA publishing models, potentially catalysed by recent funding policies and scholarly communication trends.

Figure 26: Plan S-Compliant Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (level 2)

The analysis of Plan S compliance across FoS reveals notable variances within specific disciplines (FoS level 1) that require attention. The data underscores that a one-size-fits-all approach to OA compliance may not be sufficient. Instead, nuanced strategies that account for the unique characteristics and needs of each field will likely be more effective.

Commented [CF60]: level 1 or level 2?

Commented [GU61R60]: Within level 1

Commented [CF62]: This conclusion is unclear to me. Is the conclusion that all disciplines shouldn't have the same OA compliance requirements? Or that advocacy and outreach on OA compliance for specific disciplines should not be the same?

Commented [CF63R62]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU64R62]: It's supposed to mean that to reach be OA compliant disciplines need different strategies that respond to their publication practices.

2.3.2 APCs & Transformative Agreements

The current landscape of APCs and Transformative Agreements within the realm of peer-reviewed publications presents a complex picture. Out of the **85,288** peer-reviewed publications that incurred an APC, only **1.4%** has APC data available (as reported by institutions to OpenAPC²¹), signalling a significant gap in data transparency and accountability. This lack of comprehensive data hampers our ability to fully understand and accurately extrapolate the financial aspects of OA publishing, underscoring a pressing need for more robust reporting mechanisms. Moreover, it is unclear who incurred the costs of these APCs.

²¹ <https://openapc.net/>

Table 13: APCs & Transformative Agreements Overview

Peer-Reviewed publications that incurred an APC	85,288
Peer-Reviewed publications under Transformative Agreement no APCs	1,477
Peer-Reviewed publications with APC data available from OpenAPC	1,194 (1.4% of all PR pubs with APCs)
Total APCs incurred from OpenAPC – unclear who covered the APC	EUR 2.2Mi
Average APC per publication	EUR 2,200
Average APC for Gold OA vs Hybrid OA	EUR 1,813 vs. EUR 2,756

Commented [CF65]: As above, querying why this number does not align with OpenAPC data.

Commented [GU66R65]: Fixing it.

The average APC per publication, based on the data available, stands at approximately **EUR 2,200**, with hybrid OA average APC at **EUR 2,756** versus the much lower rate for gold OA at **EUR 1,813**. However, given the low coverage of APC data, this figure should be approached with caution. It serves not as a definitive metric but rather as a preliminary indicator of the financial commitments associated with OA publishing.

Figure 27: Total APCs (EUR) of Irish OA Peer-Reviewed Publications over time

A historical overview of total APCs reveals a rising trajectory from 2008, peaking in 2017 with over **EUR 1 million** incurred, before experiencing a decline in subsequent years. This might indicate either a significant drop in APC-funded publications, a disparity in reporting, or a shift towards more Transformative Agreements that do not require direct APC payments.

Delving into journal-specific APC expenditures, we observe that top-tier journals like Nature Communications and PLOS ONE lead in APC amounts, reflecting their standing in the publishing industry and possibly the perceived value they offer in terms of impact and visibility. The prominence of journals with a medical or scientific focus such as The Lancet, Neurology, and Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology suggests a high investment in disseminating medical research findings, possibly due to the urgency and societal value attributed to these fields.

These observations underscore a multifaceted scenario where high-profile journals command significant APCs, potentially creating barriers to OA publishing for researchers with limited funding, [such as low- and middle-income countries](#). As the scholarly community grapples with these financial aspects, the role of Transformative Agreements becomes increasingly pertinent.

Figure 28: Top 20 Journals by Total APCs (EUR) of Irish OA Peer-Reviewed Publications

Figure 29: Average APCs (EUR) of Irish OA Peer-Reviewed Publications by FoS (levels 1 & 2)

The examination of average APCs across different scientific disciplines reveals distinct trends. Medical and Health Sciences tend to incur higher APCs, potentially reflective of the premium placed on immediate and OA to health-related research. Conversely, fields like Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences, Social Sciences, and Humanities tend to encounter lower APCs. The Natural Sciences display the broadest variation, with some sub-disciplines exceeding average APCs and others falling below, hinting at diverse funding mechanisms and publication practices within the field. This data is crucial for understanding the financial dynamics of OA publishing and can inform targeted support for researchers navigating APCs.

With APCs vs Under Transformative Agreements (TAs)

Transformative Agreements represent a strategic shift towards making research openly available without direct cost to the authors. In 2021, there was a marked uptick in the percentage of publications covered by TAs, accounting for **12.2%** of total output. This shift towards TAs illustrates a commitment to broadening access to scholarly work and dismantling financial barriers to publication.

Figure 30: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with APCs vs under Transformative Agreements over Time

Commented [CF67]: This is incorrect. The OpenAPC data has more publications in 2022 for Ireland. Please review and update conclusions throughout.

Commented [GU68R67]: Yes.

The advantage of TAs seems to extend more significantly to Social Sciences, which benefit from a higher proportion of TA-covered publications relative to their overall output. This is notable as it suggests that TAs could be playing a vital role in supporting disciplines that may have historically faced challenges in securing funding for OA publication fees.

Within specific fields, a closer look reveals a varied impact. Disciplines such as education and political science appear to gain considerable benefits, potentially reflecting their engagement with and support for TAs. In the STEM categories, fields like chemical sciences, nanotechnology, and other medical sciences also show a higher relative uptake of TA benefits, which may be influenced by the research culture and funding models within these disciplines.

Figure 31: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with APCs vs under Transformative Agreements by FoS (level 1)

Figure 32: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications with APCs vs under Transformative Agreements by FoS (level 2)

While these observations are indicative of positive trends, they also point to the need for a nuanced understanding of the distribution and effectiveness of TAs. The disparities in benefit across disciplines suggest that while TAs are an important tool in the OA toolkit, they may not be a one-size-fits-all solution. It is crucial to continue monitoring these trends and adjusting strategies to ensure that the promise of TAs—in terms of equity, access, and impact—is fully realized across the entire spectrum of scholarly research.

2.4 Main Findings

The analysis of OA in Ireland paints a multifaceted picture of the current state and progression of scholarly communication. This section synthesizes the key observations and insights derived from our extensive review, highlighting both the achievements and the areas needing attention to further advance OA in Ireland.

1. Scholarly Production and Research Landscape

- Among the total **418,322** Irish publications, **329,308 (78.7%)** are peer-reviewed, reflecting a strong emphasis on academic rigor and quality.
- A consistent upward trend in peer-reviewed output highlights a dynamic research environment and increased digital practices like DOIs and repository usage.
- Fields of Science (FoS) analysis reveals that Natural Sciences, Clinical Medicine, and Health Sciences are prolific in peer-reviewed publications. Engineering and Technology also exhibit substantial scholarly activity.
- Social Sciences and Humanities, while not as voluminous, demonstrate rich diversity, suggesting a need for more focused support in these areas.
- Journals remain the primary source for hosting peer-reviewed publications, but there is a growing engagement with repositories, indicating an evolving landscape of research dissemination.

Commented [CF69]: same comment as above.

Commented [GU70R69]: Will clarify.

2. Open Access and Licensing

- **38.6%** of Irish peer-reviewed publications are OA with a license, aligning with the Budapest Open Access Initiative's definition. However, **17.6%** are OA without a license, and **26.3%** are still Closed Access, signalling the need for more widespread adoption of OA practices.
- The trend analysis shows a progressive shift towards OA with licenses, but the persistence of Closed Access publications indicates ongoing challenges in transitioning away from traditional models.
- The discrepancies in licensing practices across different types of publications highlight systemic issues within the publishing industry that need addressing.

3. OA Routes and Publishing Models

- Publisher-mediated OA, comprising Gold and Hybrid OA, is predominant over repository-mediated OA. This underscores the significant impact of publishers in the Irish OA landscape.
- A rising trend in Hybrid OA suggests a shift in journal policies, potentially influenced by Transformative Agreements and Journals.
- The FoS analysis indicates that Medical and Health Sciences lead in publisher-mediated OA, while Social Sciences and Humanities benefit proportionately more from Transformative Agreements and Journals.

4. Plan S Compliance and Transformative Agreements

- A majority of Plan S compliant publications are Gold OA with APCs, but a notable portion is also under Transformative Agreements. This shows an embrace of transitional strategies towards full OA.
- Disparities in Plan S compliance across different FoS suggest the need for tailored approaches to OA compliance.
- Transformative Agreements are increasingly significant, particularly in Social Sciences and Humanities, indicating a strategic shift in these fields towards OA publishing models.

5. Article Processing Charges (APCs)

- The average APC per publication is approximately **EUR 2,200**, with a marked increase in APCs over time. However, data coverage on APCs is low, limiting the scope for comprehensive analysis.
- Variations in average APCs across FoS highlight distinct trends and financial dynamics in OA publishing, with Medical and Health Sciences incurring higher APCs.

6. FAIR Principles and Metadata Completeness²²

- Licensing analysis reveals a mix of restrictive and more open Creative Commons licenses, indicating a gradual shift towards open research practices.
- Persistent identifiers (PIDs) like DOIs show **100% coverage**, with an increasing trend in using multiple PIDs per publication, suggesting a diversifying digital ecosystem.

Commented [CF71]: Questioning this conclusion - if the report only looks at publications with DOIs, then 100% of what the report looks at will have a DOI. This doesn't necessarily mean that all relevant publications have DOIs.

The conclusion here could be clearer to be sure there's no ambiguity.

Commented [GU72R71]: This is an error, they are publications without DOIs we will update this.

²² A discussion of data quality for key metadata elements of interest for OA monitoring is presented in Section 4.

- The rising use of ORCID iDs reflects greater engagement in managing digital scholarly identity and highlights the importance of visibility and recognition in scholarly communication.

Overall Observations

Ireland's scholarly landscape is actively adapting to new norms and expectations in OA. While some fields are advancing in licensed OA, others, particularly in Humanities and Agricultural Sciences, lag, often constrained by traditional publication models and data representation. The trends indicate a positive shift towards more open and transparent research practices, but the persistence of Closed Access publications and disparities in licensing practices call for continued efforts to foster a more open scholarly communication environment.

The rise of Hybrid OA, the sustained presence of Gold OA, and the growing importance of Transformative Agreements showcase a publishing sphere adjusting to evolving mandates and researcher needs. Monitoring these changes is essential to ensure that the benefits of OA are maximized for the entire scholarly community. The disparities across disciplines and the varied impact of Transformative Agreements highlight the need for nuanced and field-specific strategies to effectively transition to more open and accessible research models.

In conclusion, while significant progress has been made towards OA in Ireland, there remains a need for continued advocacy, policy intervention, and strategic support to address the remaining challenges and disparities. This will ensure that the entire spectrum of scholarly research benefits from the principles and practices of Open Access.

3 Methodology

This section provides an outline of the methodological steps taken to conduct the analysis of OA in Ireland presented in the previous section. This transparent approach ensures the integrity and reliability of our findings.

3.1 OpenAIRE Graph: Foundation of the Monitor

The Monitor is built upon the OpenAIRE Graph (<https://graph.openaire.eu>, the Graph from here on). An open resource that aggregates a collection of research data properties (metadata, links) available for funders, organizations, researchers, research communities and publishers to interlink information by using a semantic graph database approach.

The Graph includes around metadata records for about **240 million** research products from more than **129K** trusted scholarly communication sources worldwide, including Crossref, Unpaywall, ORCID, institutional and thematic repositories (registered in OpenDOAR, re3data.org and FAIRSharing.org), Open Access journals, data archives, and the EOSC Service Catalogue. These metadata records are harvested and enriched with links between research results and projects, author affiliations, subject classifications, and links to domain-specific databases using dedicated inference algorithms. OpenAIRE's metadata records are cleaned, deduplicated, enriched, and transformed according to the OpenAIRE internal metadata model, generating the final OpenAIRE Graph. A new version of the OpenAIRE Graph is available every month. The OpenAIRE Graph is available for download and reuse under a CC-BY licence.

Commented [GU73]: How are predatory publishers weeded out?

Figure 33: The Monitor and the OpenAIRE Graph Pipeline

3.2 The Publication Set of the Monitor

This section outlines the processes through which the Monitor and this Report compile and utilize data from Irish Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organizations (RFOs), ensuring comprehensive representation of Irish peer-reviewed publications.

We take the following steps:

1. Identify Irish RPOs and their publications.
2. Identify Irish RFOs and their publications.
3. Exclude non-peer-reviewed publications.
4. Make sure PIDs are used for Irish RPOs, RFOs and publications.

The final set for the Monitor currently includes **329,308** peer-reviewed publications.

Identification of Irish Research Performing Organisations' (RPOs) Publications

The Monitor leverages the comprehensive affiliation information already present in the Graph to identify Irish RPO research output. The provenance of affiliation links in the Graph includes

1. Institutional data sources registered in OpenAIRE (repositories, CRIS, Open Access Journals)
2. Metadata from harvested data sources such as Crossref.
3. Inferred links via text mining.
4. Links created via the claim and link functionalities in OpenAIRE EXPLORE²³.

By consolidating the RPO list provided by IReL through the "National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity" and cross-referencing it with the associated RPOs within Ireland on the OpenAIRE Graph, we have created a list of Irish RPOs for the Monitor. Currently, there are approximately 1700 RPOs that require further refinement to deduplicate entries²⁴.

Irish Institutional Data Sources Registered in OpenAIRE

Institutional data sources (1. above) provide direct affiliation information to the OpenAIRE Graph, i.e. a publication from an institutional source is immediately given the corresponding affiliation. We present the coverage of Irish institutional data sources in the Monitor below²⁵.

Table 14: Irish Institutional Data Sources & Alignment with OpenAIRE

Data Source Type	Registered in OpenAIRE		Harvested by OpenAIRE (directly or via a compatible aggregator)		Not registered but Harvested by OpenAIRE (for the purposes of the Monitor)	
	# sources	# publications	# sources	# publications	# sources	# publications

²³ These functionalities, also available in the Monitor, allow users to claim research products as their own and add them to their synced ORCID record and to link research products with other research products, communities, or project. <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/how-it-works/user-actions#adding>

²⁴ See Section 5.1.

²⁵ The Appendix describes steps taken by OpenAIRE to harvest repositories and subsequent steps to follow to ensure better coverage in the Monitor.

Data Source Type	Registered in OpenAIRE		Harvested by OpenAIRE (directly or via a compatible aggregator)		Not registered but Harvested by OpenAIRE (for the purposes of the Monitor)	
	Count	Publications	Count	Publications	Count	Publications
Institutional Repositories	14	183,961	0	0	7	8,209
Thematic/ Publication Repositories	2	3,697	0	0	0	0
CRIS Systems	0	0	0	0	0	0
OA Journals	0	0	18	2,628	0	0

Among the registered Irish Institutional Repositories within OpenAIRE, a cumulative count of **183,961** publications is recorded. There are **3** repositories that are compliant with the version 3.0 of the OpenAIRE Guidelines. **10** (plus **1** Thematic Repository) adhere to the BASIC and to version 2.0 of the OpenAIRE Guidelines. Consequently, these repositories do not conform to the most recent IT and repository standards, which necessitate more contextually enriched content, including links and associations with various research outputs and entities. Furthermore, they do not accommodate diverse and enhanced vocabularies. These repositories also fall short of alignment with Open Science mandates and established standards, as they do not endorse well-established metadata schemas and namespace abbreviations for project identifications, including EC funding programs, among others.

Identification of Irish Research Funding Organisations' (RFOs) Publications

To guarantee a thorough representation of funded research outputs, the OpenAIRE Graph establishes links between publications and their associated funding data through a variety of methods:

- Harvesting links from repositories, OA Journals, CRIS systems.
- Merging information from Crossref's Open Funder Registry (OFR)²⁶.
- Collecting links from users via the "link" functionality²⁷.
- Exchanging data with the EC's IT systems for EC/FP funding.
- Text mining of full text publications to identify the grants for 30+ funders that have joined OpenAIRE (see next paragraph). Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) is one of them.

²⁶ <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

²⁷ <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/how-it-works/user-actions#linking>

Irish Funders in OpenAIRE

Irish funders are represented in the OpenAIRE graph through two primary avenues. The first is by directly joining OpenAIRE²⁸, a process that entails providing a comprehensive list of research projects, the creation of a tailored text mining algorithm for data extraction, and meticulous curation of project-publication links to ensure accuracy. Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) has successfully undergone this process.

Table 15: Irish Funders that have joined OpenAIRE

Irish RFOs that have joined OpenAIRE	Projects	Publications
Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	6,385	19,505

The second avenue for representation is through the OFR using the funders' fundref IDs. While this allows funders to be associated with publications via valid DOIs in the OpenAIRE Graph, it does not offer the granularity of the direct integration, notably the curated project-publication links.

Table 16: General Representation of Irish Funders in OpenAIRE (excluding SFI)

# Irish RFOs integrated via OFR	# Irish RFOs integrated via OFR with links to publications	# Irish RFOs' publications (excluding SFI)
142	79	15,370

For a funder to achieve the detailed representation observed with SFI, a direct integration with OpenAIRE is recommended. This not only ensures a comprehensive presence but also guarantees the precision of the data incorporated.

Peer-Reviewed Publications

We refine the set of Irish publications, as detailed in the preceding section, by focusing only on peer-reviewed articles, based on the following criteria:

1. **Curated Peer-Review Assessment:** The OpenAIRE team has engaged in a curation process to determine the peer-review status of journals. This hand-curated assessment has been integrated into the Graph and is continuously under development.

Commented [CF74]: The content of this section seems to be about peer-reviewed articles, but the section title and table title say "Peer-Reviewed Publications". Request clarification - if it's only peer-reviewed articles, please state articles and not publications (more generally)

Commented [GU75R74]: No it is not only articles.

Commented [CF76R74]: Noting that the first sentence states "focusing only on peer-reviewed articles", please update/clarify where appropriate in the text.

²⁸ <https://www.openaire.eu/funders-how-to-join-guide>

- 2. Exclusion of Grey Literature:** We also filter out 'grey literature', which includes document types that typically bypass the peer review process, such as reports, theses, and white papers. Given that the OpenAIRE Graph aggregates data from various sources, resulting in merged records, we specifically exclude entries where all instances are identified as grey literature.
- 3. Presence of DOI from Crossref:** Since Crossref predominantly catalogues peer-reviewed content, its DOIs help maintain the scholarly credibility of our included publications.

The combination of these three criteria gives the following number of Irish peer-reviewed publications of the Monitor.

Table 17: Irish Peer-Reviewed Publications

Irish peer-reviewed publications
329,308

Additional Criteria Under Examination

Beyond the core criteria, we are actively delving into additional parameters that might further refine our identification process.

- Presence of DOI from DataCite:** We are ascertaining if such an inclusion can offer breadth to our dataset. The examples of peer-reviewed publications that we found with a DOI issued by DataCite were so far **all identified** as peer-reviewed in OpenAIRE even without including this selection criterion. We will continue to examine this option and our system is flexible to incorporate it.
- Reference Count by Field of Study (FOS):** We also investigated the potential for establishing a reference count threshold, beneath which a publication might be classified as non-peer-reviewed. However, the analysis of mean and standard deviation of reference counts within each Field of Science (FoS) level revealed significant variability. This variability precludes the adoption of a uniform criterion based on reference count. We plan to continue our exploration in this area to refine our assessment criteria.

Use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

To achieve accurate and comprehensive monitoring of Irish scholarly publications, we place emphasis on the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs). PIDs serve as essential building blocks, allowing us to uniquely identify these publications, facilitating the discoverability, accessibility, and reusability of research outputs.

The Monitor specifically defines an Irish scholarly publication as one that contains a persistent identifier (PID) associated with an Irish organization. These PIDs can be found in various places within the publication's metadata, PID metadata, or even within the publication content itself. We seamlessly integrate a range of PIDs for both research outputs and organizations. The process of deduplication ensures that metadata records from different data sources are effectively merged, accompanied by publicly displayed provenance information. This comprehensive approach guarantees not only the widest possible coverage but also maintains the integrity and consistency of our data.

The table below provides an overview of the PIDs used for publications, organizations, and authors within the Monitor, along with the corresponding number of publications associated with each type of PID.

Table 18: Irish peer-reviewed publications by PID type

PID type	# Irish peer-reviewed publications
Publication PIDs	
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	299,427
Handle	49,663
PubMed Central ID	40,529
PubMed ID	110,941
arXiv	11,838
Organisation PIDs	
Participant Identification Code	265,779
ISNI	429,753
OrgRef	409,025
Open Funder Registry	386,971
Wikidata	429,394
GRID	436,551
RingGold	25,497
ROR	437,179
OrgReg	404,132
ORCID iDs	
ORCID iD	173,495

3.3 Data Disambiguation Techniques

Deduplication in OpenAIRE: The OpenAIRE Graph collects metadata records about scholarly works from different providers, which can carry different information. To provide accurate statistics, OpenAIRE merges duplicate records of the same scholarly work. The deduplication process is described in detail in the following link: <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/deduplication/>

Organizations: Organizations within OpenAIRE are aggregated from diverse registries and undergo a deduplication process via OpenOrgs. This tool merges automation with a "human in the loop" mechanism. It is designed to cluster records that are more likely to be analogous, employing both URL-based and title-based functions. Through the process of grouping duplicates, representative organizations not only inherit all attributes from the combined records but also maintain a record of their origin. On the Monitor, managers overseeing the National, RPO, and RFO dashboards will have access to OpenOrgs, empowering them to deduplicate Irish RPO records.

Journals, Publishers, and Licences: To ensure precision and reliability in its data, the Monitor disambiguates journals using their ISSN numbers and publishers through the utilization of Crossref metadata, including ROR IDs and DOI prefixes, among other identifiers. This effort will be bolstered by custom text similarity algorithms.

Additionally, OpenAIRE is systematically working on normalizing licences. Currently, about **98%** of licences in the November version of the Graph have been successfully grouped and normalized. However, accurately comparing and categorizing these licences, especially non-Creative Commons (non-CC) ones, remains a challenge.

Authors: Researcher dashboards²⁹ are fully integrated with ORCID profiles, streamlining the identification process by linking directly to researchers' ORCID IDs. This integration accounts for all name variations associated with a researcher's ORCID ID, ensuring accurate and comprehensive representation. When researchers log in using their ORCID ID, they can easily claim additional research outputs. These claims, once made, synchronize with their ORCID profile, and are updated in both the ORCID system and the Monitor with the monthly update of the OpenAIRE Graph. This seamless connection between the two platforms guarantees that researchers have consistent and visible access to their entire body of work.

Commented [CF77]: RPO and RFO records? Or only RPO records?

Commented [GU78R77]: RPO

Commented [CF79R77]: To clarify: RFOs can not deduplicate their records? This seems like it should be enabled?

²⁹ <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/researcher>

3.4 Enrichment via Text Mining

To enrich metadata and enhance the comprehensiveness of scholarly records, OpenAIRE employs several effective text-mining methods. These methods include:

- **Affiliation Matching:** This process involves matching affiliations extracted from PDF and XML documents with organizations listed in the OpenAIRE organization database.
- **Funding Classifiers:** Utilizing a document classification algorithm, OpenAIRE analyses free text from abstracts of publications to categorize scientific text into one or more predefined content classes, such as funders and projects.
- **Extraction of Acknowledged Concepts:** OpenAIRE scans plaintexts of publications to identify acknowledged concepts. These may include grant identifiers (projects) from funders, accession numbers of bioentities, mentions of EPO (European Patent Office) patents, and custom concepts that link research objects to specific research communities and initiatives within OpenAIRE.
- **Metadata Extraction:** OpenAIRE employs the CERMINE project to extract plaintext and metadata from PDF documents. This extraction process covers various aspects, including titles, authors, affiliations, abstracts, keywords, journal names, volume, and issue information, parsed bibliographic references, as well as the structure of document sections, section titles, and paragraphs.

The OpenAIRE PDF aggregation system was strategically redirected to prioritize the collection of PDFs from Irish Open Access (OA) publications. Consequently, we verified **84K** URLs (out of **185,008** peer-reviewed OA publications) and successfully retrieved **61K** PDFs from these. As the OpenAIRE PDF aggregation system operates continuously, we expect the number of successfully retrieved PDFs to grow steadily over time.

These documents were then processed through the Graph pipeline, facilitating the implementation of the text-mining methods mentioned earlier. Additionally, we mined these documents for classification into Fields of Science (FoS) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as well as to identify corresponding author affiliations. The methodology for the latter is detailed in Section 3.6.

FoS (FoS) Classification System: To categorize into distinct levels FoS³⁰, we have integrated an advanced classification system (Kotitsas, et al. 2023³¹). This system utilizes Natural Language Processing (NLP) to analyse various components of the OpenAIRE Graph, including abstracts, citations, references, and venues. As a result, each publication is systematically classified into FoS classes down to level 3, adding precision to its scientific domain. This hierarchical categorization not only provides a structured framework but also bolsters our ability to pinpoint multidisciplinary overlaps within the research.

SDG Classification System: To contextualize the impact of research on addressing paramount global challenges, we have incorporated a classification mechanism aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This schema is engineered to elucidate the alignment of research endeavours with critical issues, ranging from climate adaptation, biodiversity preservation, mitigation of environmental contaminants, to socioeconomic upliftment.

3.5 Indicators

The table below presents the construction methodology of indicators included in this Report, offering a detailed look at how each indicator is derived and calculated. The definitions of these indicators are given in the Glossary³².

Table 19: Construction methodology of indicators

Attribute	Construction Methodology
Under Transformative Agreements	We have identified and retrieved from OpenAPC (IReL OpenAPC Dataset ³³) the set of articles with metadata published under Transformative Agreements for Ireland.
Journal Business Models	
OA (Gold)	Utilizing OpenAIRE's curated Gold ISSN list, Unpaywall metadata, and DOAJ journals.
Diamond OA	We obtain journal-level APC data from DOAJ using DOAJ's Public Data Dump (an exportable version of the journal metadata). We cross-

Commented [CF80]: Footnote URL doesn't resolve. Correct link: https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapc-de/tree/master/data/transformative_agreements/IReL

Commented [GU81R80]: Thank you

³⁰ The taxonomy is presented here: <https://explore.openaire.eu/fields-of-science>

³¹ Kotitsas, S., Pappas, D., Manola, N., & Papageorgiou, H. (2023). SCINOBO: a novel system classifying scholarly communication in a dynamically constructed hierarchical Field-of-Science taxonomy. *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, 8, 1149834.

³² The indicators on the Monitor are described here <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/terminology#entities>

³³ https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapcde/tree/master/data/Transformative_agreements/IReL

Attribute	Construction Methodology
	reference this with the OpenAPC data integrated in the OpenAIRE Graph.
Subscription	Journals without any open access articles.
Hybrid	Journals with open access articles that are not OA journals.
Transformative	We identify Transformative Journals by ISSN matching with the publicly available Transformative Journals data ³⁴ from Plan S initiative.
OA Routes/Colours	
Green OA with Licence	An open access scholarly publication deposited in a repository. It may be published version or preprint, and must be accompanied by a specified licence that outlines how the material can be used, shared, and distributed.
Gold OA	A scientific publication published in an OA journal as defined above.
Hybrid OA	An open access scientific publication published in a hybrid journal with an open licence.
Unrealised OA	
Bronze	An open access scientific publication published in a Hybrid journal without an open licence.
Green without licence	An open access scholarly publication deposited in a repository. It may be published version or preprint, without a specified licence.
Accessibility – Interoperability	
Accessible	Accessible publications are sourced from OpenAIRE's full text collection, which holds PDFs of over twenty million OA publications. OpenAIRE's PDF aggregation system, recalibrated to prioritize Irish publications, examines the URL links in each publication's metadata to retrieve the corresponding PDF document. Given that multiple links can be associated with one publication, each is navigated. With ongoing automation, the system's coverage consistently expands, verifying if OA publications are accessible through thorough URL link inspection and PDF retrieval.
Interoperable	The construction of interoperable publications within the Monitor is intrinsically tied to their accessibility. Since we systematically fetch PDFs, any publication that is accessible through this process is also considered interoperable. In essence, the minimum threshold for interoperability is met

Commented [CF82]: Request to update this to specify how OpenAIRE identifies hybrid journals (this is a description of what a hybrid journal is).

Commented [GU83R82]: That's how we identify them. We identify all OA journals, then any additional journal that has an OA article is hybrid. We use ISSNs for deduplication.

Commented [CF84]: Request to update this to specify how OpenAIRE identifies these definitions (this is a description of what a these OA routes/colours/unrealised OA, but not a description of HOW you identify them).

Commented [GU85R84]: we identify them as described, but we can try to elaborate more

³⁴ <https://journalcheckertool.org/Transformative-journals/>

Attribute	Construction Methodology
	when a publication's full text is accessible in a machine-readable format through the PDF aggregation system.

3.6 Additional Aspects

In this section, we outline the construction methodologies for additional metadata elements requested. While the subsequent Data Evaluation section delves into a comprehensive analysis of all key elements, here we focus solely on those requiring construction methodologies that have not been previously addressed.

Corresponding author affiliation: In identifying the corresponding author's affiliation within the Graph, we encounter limitations due to the lack of explicit tagging for this role in metadata from integrated data sources. While some sources are developing to provide such details, we have implemented the following methodologies to address this gap.

- **Contributor Rank Analysis:** This method involves identifying the corresponding author based on their position in the author list. Typically, we consider the first author as the corresponding author if the list is **not** alphabetical. However, sequencing of authors is rarely represented in metadata, limiting the effectiveness of this approach. Using this method, we have identified the first author in only **0.04%** of Irish peer-reviewed publications.
- **Text Mining: (ongoing)** Specifically for Irish publications, text mining is employed on PDFs to discern the corresponding author's affiliation. This method is applicable only for OA publications where PDFs are available. Of the PDFs received, a fraction could not be processed. Among the processed PDFs, only about **8%** mentioned "corresponding" or "correspondence" on the first page, that is **1.5%** of all OA peer-reviewed publications. Future steps include employing advanced tools for PDF processing that utilize machine learning and computer vision. Additionally, we plan to search for alternative tags that might indicate the corresponding author, such as "mailto" or publisher-specific tags.
- **IReL OpenAPC Dataset³⁵:** The dataset, which encompasses publications published under Transformative Agreements, includes valuable information on the institutions of corresponding authors. It contributes to our analysis with **1821** publications, representing **0.5%** of Irish peer-reviewed publications. It offers a unique insight, particularly in the context of Transformative Agreements, enhancing our understanding of the corresponding author affiliations within the broader landscape of Irish academic research.

Commented [CF86]: incomplete figures from the OpenAPC dataset

Commented [GU87R86]: Yes

³⁵ https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapcde/tree/master/data/Transformative_agreements/IReL

Together, these approaches represent our continuous effort to enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of corresponding author information in the Graph. As we refine these methodologies and examine alternative approaches, we expect to see an improvement in the identification of corresponding authors, thereby enriching the dataset, and enhancing the utility of the Monitor for various stakeholders.

Publicly-funded: To identify Irish scholarly publications that align with the definition of "publicly funded research as research undertaken in whole or in part via publicly funded resourcing or remuneration, e.g., salaries, grants, contracts, etc.," several steps are underway:

1. We used the responses for the publicly funded RPOs/RFOs from the National Open Access Monitor Survey conducted by IReL.
2. We also utilised OFR's metadata to identify publicly funded RFOs with the "Government" type. OFR's metadata offers pertinent information on funder type which is being integrated in the Graph.

Methodological Concerns: As per the tender's definition, any publication from an RPO partially funded by the government is categorized as publicly-funded. This categorization impacts the Monitor's data: such publications are marked as publicly-funded in all associated RPO profiles, *regardless of each institution's direct receipt of public funding.*

Table 20: # and % of Irish Publicly-Funded Publications

# Irish publications	418,322
# and % of Irish publicly-funded Publications	284,781 (68.1%)

4 Data Evaluation & Challenges

This section presents a critical assessment of various metadata elements and their associated challenges. The findings outlined here are instrumental in understanding the current landscape of data quality and integrity, which are pivotal in shaping effective Open Access monitoring and policy development.

Commented [CF88]: Include reference here to National Action Plan, page 12
<https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

Commented [GU89R88]: Will do

Commented [CF90]: I don't understand the issue here, in the way that it's been described.

Would appreciate discussion and clarification at the meeting please.

Commented [GU91R90]: Sure

Commented [CF92R90]: For further discussion at the meeting

Key Highlights

Inconsistencies in Metadata: A prevalent issue across multiple metadata elements is the inconsistency in data entry, naming conventions, and standardization. This particularly affects the accurate identification of Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), publishers, journals, and licences.

Complexities in Licence Reporting: The challenges in licence reporting are twofold. First, there is a notable gap in including licences in metadata, which is crucial because OA publications without a licence cannot be accurately classified as OA. Second, understanding the nuances in licensing, specifically the mapping between various licences and their levels of openness, is complex. This affects our ability to clearly determine the openness of publications and complicates efforts to standardize and categorize Open Access statuses effectively.

Challenges in Timely Reporting, Indexing, and Use of ORCID iDs: Our analysis reveals critical gaps, especially in the timely reporting and indexing of the most recent year's publication data, along with comprehensive utilization of ORCID iDs for authors. These issues pose significant challenges in accurately capturing and reflecting research outputs and their impacts.

Variability in Access Rights and Version Identification: The dynamic nature of access rights, such as transitions from embargoed to open access status, and the difficulty in distinguishing between different publication versions (pre-prints vs. Version of Record), complicates the metadata landscape.

Linkage of Funding and Research Outputs: Establishing robust links between funding sources, specifically for funders not in OpenAIRE, and research outputs remains a challenge, highlighting the need for enhanced methodologies in RFO reporting practices, data harvesting and text mining.

URLs to PDF Full Texts: A significant portion of OA peer-reviewed publications lack valid URLs to full-text PDFs, impacting the ease of access for researchers and the potential for text mining.

Corresponding Author Affiliation: The challenge of accurately identifying corresponding author affiliations points to broader issues in metadata reporting and standardization across different sources.

Commented [CF93]: Please clarify if the Report and the Monitor are using Unpaywall to categorise Open Access statuses, and if not, why not.

Commented [CF94R93]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU95R93]: We construct it by ourselves because we have more records than UW.

Commented [CF96]: this has been a historic issue when using Scopus and Web of Science, but when looking at open data, one would assume that the metadata is open and available when the article is published open (i.e. immediately). If this isn't the case, please provide some information on why this is not the case.

Commented [CF97R96]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU98R96]: Metadata is open.

Knowing when something was deposited in a repository is not a common metadata element.

We will refine the text.

These findings underscore the need for concerted efforts in improving metadata quality and the implementation of standardized practices across the board. OpenAIRE is equipped with tools and methodologies that are designed to address these challenges, offering solutions to enhance data integrity and standardization. The challenges identified are not insular but interconnected, impacting the overall efficacy of the Monitor at large. Addressing these challenges, by following Open Science best practices, the FAIR principles and with the support of OpenAIRE's resources, is imperative for ensuring the integrity and utility of Open Access monitoring and research analytics.

In the following table, we will delve deeper into each metadata element, exploring the specific challenges and implications in detail, setting the stage for the subsequent recommendations and solutions.

Table 21: Metadata Analysis

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
Affiliations: Identification and association of research publications to Irish RPOs	The OpenAIRE Graph currently includes 329,308 peer-reviewed publications affiliated with Irish RPOs. Efforts to ensure high-quality data include advanced source ingestion, deduplication processes, and continuous data validation ³⁶ .	Accurate affiliations are essential for tracking Ireland's research output. 43.8% of Irish publications are from OpenAIRE's harvested institutional data sources (repositories, CRIS, OA journals), emphasizing the role of repositories and journals in data integrity. The rest, derived from external metadata (such as Crossref), text mining, and OpenAIRE EXPLORE's claim and link functions ³⁷ highlight the need for diverse data inputs to capture the full scope of Irish research activities. The primary challenge in identifying affiliation links is that many data sources do not provide this information in their metadata or provide strings in place of PIDs describing the affiliations.
RPOs Name: Accurate Identification of RPO names and all their variants	The OpenAIRE Graph currently lists 1,721 Irish organisations, suggesting duplicates due to naming variations and frequent updates.	Accurately identifying RPOs is vital for correctly linking research outputs to specific Monitor profiles. The challenge lies in the diversity of naming conventions and frequent updates, which can lead to duplicates and misidentification. OpenAIRE addresses this by employing PIDs and other deduplication methods.

³⁶ The latest version of the Graph includes over 79 million affiliations (>140Mi in total when counting multiple affiliations) out of 242 million research outputs (publications, datasets, software, other research products).

³⁷ Both available in the Monitor as well.

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
		Additionally, the OpenOrgs tool, available to RPO dashboard managers, plays a crucial role in refining RPO profiles, ensuring accurate labelling of departments and affiliated entities. The complexity of managing and standardizing these variations represents an ongoing challenge in maintaining data integrity.
Funded publications: Establishing comprehensive funder-publication links.	While SFI (Science Foundation Ireland) is curated due to having joined OpenAIRE, for other public funders, we rely on OFR harvested metadata. Its quality is difficult to assess externally.	Establishing clear links between funders and publications is crucial for accurate research tracking and measuring of OA compliance to various funder mandates. Funders that join OpenAIRE provide a list of projects, enabling us to develop dedicated text mining algorithms. These algorithms achieve near-perfect precision in identifying project-publication links and improve the quality of harvested metadata, enhancing the accuracy of funder-publication connections in the OpenAIRE Graph ³⁸ .
Grant award ID: Ensuring availability & establishing project-publication links.	For SFI-funded projects, there is full coverage of Grant Award IDs, enabling the inference of project-publication links. Other funders in OFR that have not joined OpenAIRE currently lack these specific links, offering only funder-publication connections in the harvested data.	Project-publication links are crucial for assessing compliance and providing detailed insights for funders. The main challenge is the lack of uniform reporting standards among funders, complicating text mining and metadata harvesting for precise project-publication connections. OpenAIRE is developing dedicated algorithms for the Irish Research Council, leveraging their publicly available project metadata. ³⁹
Publicly-funded publications: Identification of all publications resulting from publicly funded research.	The Monitor includes 284,781 publicly-funded peer-reviewed publications, constituting 68.1% of the total. Quality assurance involves using the Stakeholder Survey conducted by IReL and the OFR metadata field {type}.	Identifying publicly-funded publications is essential for accurately tracking government research investments. As per the tender's definition, any publication from an RPO partially funded by the government is categorized as publicly-funded. This categorization impacts the Monitor's data: such publications, including those labelled by individuals from different RPOs, are marked as publicly-funded in all associated RPO

³⁸ <https://www.openaire.eu/funders-how-to-join-guide>

³⁹ We anticipate these enhancements to be reflected in the Monitor by February 2024, significantly improving data granularity and link accuracy.

Commented [CF99]: Following up on my previous comment - is the proposed issue here CO-AUTHORED articles, where one author is from a partially-publicly funded RPO, and the other authors aren't?

This is the intention from NORF, as I understand it, that this would be marked publicly-funded.

Commented [GU100R99]: and it is

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
		profiles, regardless of each institution's direct receipt of public funding.
Version of the Publication: Differentiating between Version of Record (VoR) and pre-print.	Assessing the quality in this aspect is challenging. 32.5% of Green OA publications labelled as articles are also marked as pre-prints, suggesting potential inconsistencies. The 'Version of Record' (VoR) is rarely included as a distinct metadata element, and the sources that do provide it offer limited coverage.	Accurately distinguishing between VoR and pre-print versions is crucial for compliance with RFO mandates that require deposition of the VoR. This differentiation also sheds light on publication practices. A possible method to infer the version type is by using the deposition date to the repository. The "Publication Date" mandatory field stated by the OpenAIRE Guidelines covers the deposition date as typically it is associated with the creation or availability of the resource.
PIDs: Identifying and ensuring consistent coverage of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for publications, organisations, and authors.	All Irish peer-reviewed publications currently have a PID ⁴⁰ . ORCID iDs are present in almost 55% of these publications.	PIDs are critical for clearly identifying research outputs and contributors, enhancing data findability and interoperability. A key challenge, however, lies in the widespread and consistent adoption of PIDs like ORCID iDs. Many authors and institutions have yet to fully embrace these identifiers, leading to gaps in PID coverage. Additionally, the integration of PIDs across various platforms and databases often faces hurdles due to different standards and systems. Actively using ORCID's sync and claim functionalities can help authors improve PID coverage, but broader adoption and standardization across the research landscape are necessary for achieving comprehensive PID integration ⁴¹ .
Peer-Reviewed publications: Verifying peer-review status of Irish publications	78.7% of publications from Irish RPOs and RFOs are identified as peer-reviewed. OpenAIRE is assessing this quality through continued data examination, including manually curated entries for	The verification of peer-reviewed status is crucial for maintaining the integrity and scholarly value of the research outputs within the Monitor. This ensures that vetted and quality-assured publications contribute to Ireland's research profile. A major challenge is the lack of a standardized 'peer-reviewed' identifier in

Commented [CF101]: This is an inappropriate statement in the Irish context.

SFI policy specifically states AAM: <https://www.sfi.ie/funding/sfi-policies-and-guidance/open-research/SFI-Open-Access-Publishing-Guide.pdf>

Plan S does not mandate VOR, and encourages RRS to deposit AAM: <https://www.coalition-s.org/faq/why-if-the-vor-is-preferred-to-the-aam-coalition-s-does-not-mandate-it/>

HRB policy specifies post-prints or VOR: <https://www.hrb.ie/funding/manage-a-grant/grant-policies/open-access/>

IRC specifies post-prints or VOR: https://research.ie/assets/uploads/2017/05/IRC_Open-Access-Policy-Final.pdf

and one of the new NORF projects is on RRS, which is AAM focused.

Please update text, and any impacting conclusions, to ensure that AAM with a license in a repository is correctly identified as green OA.

Commented [GU102R101]: It does not change anything in the numbers, we will add it to the exposition.

Commented [CF103]: As commented before - querying whether all Irish peer-reviewed publications in the OpenAIRE graph have a PID? Or ALL Irish peer-reviewed publications?

e.g. this journal doesn't use DOIs or ISSNs, or use any other PIDs that I know of - and is a peer-reviewed journal. <https://cujournal.ie/>

Commented [CF104R103]: For further discussion at the meeting

Commented [GU105R103]: They do not all have a PID

⁴⁰ Refer to the Methodology section 3.5

⁴¹ More information on PIDs in the OpenAIRE Graph is available at <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/pids-and-identifiers>

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
	peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings.	metadata, complicating the verification of publications' scholarly status ⁴² .
Year of publication: Low(er) coverage for 2022	For 2022, the OpenAIRE Graph includes 13K peer-reviewed Irish publications, compared to 22K in 2020 and 20K in 2021.	Timely inclusion of the latest publications is crucial for accurately reflecting current research trends. A key challenge is the inherent delay in publication and indexing. Research often experiences a lag between completion, publication, and eventual indexing in databases. This delay typically results in lower coverage for the most recent year, affecting the immediacy and comprehensiveness of a monitoring system.
Publisher & Journal: Challenges in deduplication	Due to variations in naming conventions, abbreviations, and metadata inconsistencies, the same publisher or journal may appear as distinct multiple entries.	Accurate and consistent representation of publishers and journals is essential for reliable bibliometric analysis. Inconsistencies in naming can lead to duplicated entries, impacting the accuracy of data and research metrics. ⁴³
Licence I: Challenges in deduplication and interpretation of licence agreements	Approximately 98% of licences in the OpenAIRE Graph have been successfully grouped and normalized, but categorizing non-CC (Creative Commons) licences remains a challenge.	Accurate categorization and interpretation of licences are vital for understanding the usage rights and restrictions of publications, which directly impacts researchers' ability to reuse and disseminate knowledge. The legal complexities and variety of non-CC licences pose significant challenges in standardizing this metadata. Efforts to clarify and correctly categorize these licences are crucial for ensuring that users have clear and correct information regarding the accessibility and reuse conditions of scholarly works.
Licence II: Incomplete Licensing in OA Metadata	17.6% of OA peer-reviewed publications in the Monitor are not associated with a specific licence.	The challenge of missing licences significantly impacts the ability to determine the true extent of Open Access in Ireland and assess its adoption among various stakeholders. Without clear licensing, it is not possible to confirm a publication's Open Access status, which is essential for comprehensive OA

⁴² For detailed information on the methodology used for determining peer-reviewed status, please refer to the Section 3.5.

⁴³ OpenAIRE's ongoing enhancements, including the refinement of algorithms using PIDs, aim to address these duplication (see Section 3.3)

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
		monitoring and for guiding data-driven decisions within the OA landscape.
FoS: Coverage and potential under-representation of specific disciplines	The FoS coverage for peer-reviewed publications in the OpenAIRE Graph is 74.7% , with 12.3% from arts, humanities, and Social Sciences. Differentiating community practices from actual research output is a key challenge in accurately assessing disciplinary representation.	Comprehensive FoS coverage is vital for equitable representation of all research disciplines. In fields like arts, humanities, and Social Sciences, a key challenge is discerning whether the lower representation is due to less research output or challenges in data harvesting. The OpenAIRE FoS classification system, continually updated, seeks to address these uncertainties but assessing the root cause of under-representation in certain disciplines is an ongoing complexity.
Access rights I: Missing data	17.07% of Irish peer-reviewed publications do not include access rights	Key for monitoring OA uptake and progress.
Access rights I: changing over time, such as an Embargoed publication becoming OA.	To the best of our knowledge, the original access rights of a publication deposited in a repository is not a metadata element that repositories expose.	Monitoring changes in access rights, such as an embargoed publication transitioning to OA, is crucial for compliance tracking and understanding the evolving accessibility of research outputs. A primary challenge is the absence of initial access right details in repository metadata, making it difficult to track the evolution of access status. OpenAIRE's approach of maintaining historical snapshots, with monthly deposits in Zenodo and visible indicator aggregates in the portal, partly addresses this challenge by enabling the observation of changes in access rights over time. However, capturing the complete trajectory of each publication's accessibility remains complex due to the initial data gaps.

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
URLs to PDF full texts: Coverage and validity of URLs linking to PDFs in publication metadata.	Of the 185K OA peer-reviewed publications in the Graph, 84K (45%) have valid URLs in their metadata, with 61K (33% of all OA peer-reviewed publications) linking directly to full-text PDFs.	Accurate URLs linking to PDF full texts are essential for ensuring metadata integrity and the true accessibility of OA publications. A key challenge here is the inconsistent or incorrect reporting of these URLs. Many publications either lack direct links to full-text PDFs or have URLs that lead to outdated or inaccessible pages. This inconsistency hampers the effectiveness of metadata in providing direct access to research content.
Corresponding author affiliation: Determining the institution of the corresponding author.	Currently, the reporting of corresponding author affiliations in the metadata is not widespread. Efforts involving text mining of full-text PDFs and the use of the OpenAPC IReL dataset ⁴⁴ have resulted in coverage of approximately 2% of all peer-reviewed publications ⁴⁵ .	Accurately identifying the corresponding author's affiliation is crucial for bibliometric analyses and understanding research collaboration networks. The major challenge lies in the inconsistent or incomplete reporting of corresponding author details in publications. This inconsistency hampers efforts to automate identification and validation processes, affecting the overall data quality.
APCs & BPCs: Lack of data availability	Of the 85,228 peer-reviewed publications that incurred an APC, only 1194 have APC data from OpenAPC (1.4%).	Understanding the financial aspects of OA publishing, particularly APCs and BPCs, is crucial for policy makers and institutions. The lack of shared APC and BPC data by publishers limits the ability to conduct comprehensive economic analyses of OA publishing, impacting budgeting and policy decisions.
Historical OA status of journals: journals changing OA status	Historical journal data is typically not available.	Accurately tracking the evolution of journals from subscription-based to hybrid or fully Open Access is vital for correctly categorizing articles. The current lack of historical data leads to potential misclassification of articles based on the journal's present status (e.g. diamond OA), affecting the accuracy of OA

⁴⁴ The dataset includes data on publications published under Transformative Agreements including the institution of the corresponding author.

https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapcde/tree/master/data/Transformative_agreements/IReL

⁴⁵ Refer to Section 3.6 for more details.

Metadata element & Issue	Quality	Relevance & Challenges
		categorization and skewing analyses of OA trends and policy development.

This detailed analysis of metadata elements and their associated challenges provides a comprehensive snapshot of the current state of data quality and integrity for Irish peer-reviewed publications, and establishes a **valuable benchmark** for future assessments. By identifying specific areas of concern and highlighting key issues, we have laid a solid foundation for measuring progress and guiding improvements. This benchmark serves as a critical reference point, enabling us to monitor advancements in metadata management and the effectiveness of OA monitoring over time. As we move forward, the insights gained from this analysis will inform the next section of the report, focusing on targeted recommendations and solutions. These will address the challenges identified, paving the way for enhanced data quality, improved standardization, and more effective Open Access practices.

5 Recommendations & Solutions

In this section, we delve into a series of strategies and recommendations aimed at enhancing OA monitoring in Ireland. Our approach unfolds across three interconnected tiers of improvement.

First, we explore direct improvement strategies, focusing on actions and tools **within the Monitor** itself that leverage OpenAIRE's functionalities for immediate enhancements in data quality and user engagement. Following this, we address **indirect improvement strategies which centre on elevating the quality of data being harvested into OpenAIRE**. These recommendations target stakeholders contributing data, with the goal of ensuring that the information feeding into the Monitor is precise, comprehensive, and up-to-date.

Concluding our approach, we examine **long-term monitoring solutions** and suggested workflows. These encompass broader, sustainable improvements that extend beyond immediate solutions, involving policy development, collaborative efforts among stakeholders, and embracing technological advancements for future challenges.

By adopting these strategies, stakeholders from various sectors of the Open Access ecosystem can collaboratively foster a more robust, accurate, and efficient monitoring system. These recommendations are designed not just to tackle current challenges but

also to establish a groundwork for ongoing enhancement and adaptability in the ever-evolving domain of research and data management.

5.1 Direct Improvement Strategies for the Monitor

To immediately and effectively enhance the quality and functionality of the Monitor, a range of direct strategies can be implemented. **These strategies leverage existing tools and functionalities within the OpenAIRE ecosystem, facilitating tangible improvements in data management and user interaction.** The following table outlines specific actions that various stakeholders can undertake. These actions are designed to directly address the challenges identified in our metadata analysis, improving data accuracy, completeness, and the overall user experience. By engaging with these strategies, stakeholders can contribute to the refinement and advancement of the Monitor, enhancing its value as a tool for Open Access monitoring and research analytics.

Table 22: Direct Improvement Strategies for the Monitor

Recommendation	Policy Makers	Publishers	RPOs	RFOs	Researchers	Institutional Repository Managers
Organisation Deduplication via OpenOrgs: regularly deduplicate RPO names and manage department/affiliated entity relationships ⁴⁶ .	X		X	X		
Join OpenAIRE: RFOs can join OpenAIRE by providing their project data for customized text mining and metadata enrichment ⁴⁷ .				X		
Registration to OpenAIRE PROVIDE: Register institutional data sources to OpenAIRE PROVIDE, follow the latest version of the OpenAIRE Guidelines, and use the						X

Commented [CF106]: Query if this is an action for policy makers? What's the logic here?

Commented [GU107R106]: Representatives from National authorities can also deduplicate national RPOs to some extent if they wish the data to be cleaner, it is just an option.

Commented [CF108R106]: For further discussion at the meeting

⁴⁶ Users who wish to perform this section need to apply to be the primary dashboard manager of their organization by completing this form <https://app.onlinesurveys.jisc.ac.uk/s/maynoothuniversity/national-open-access-monitor-dashboard-manager-application-form>.

⁴⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/funders-how-to-join-guide>

Recommendation	Policy Makers	Publishers	RPOs	RFOs	Researchers	Institutional Repository Managers
Metadata Validator and Broker services for enhanced metadata quality ⁴⁸ .						
Register with ORCID and Sync to Monitor: Register with ORCID and synchronize your ORCID and with Monitor accounts to keep both records current ⁴⁹ .					X	
Use Linking Functionality in OpenAIRE: Use Linking functionality to enrich connections within the Graph by linking research products to other researcher products, research communities or projects ⁵⁰ .	X	X	X	X	X	X
Engage with Monitor Dashboard & Provide Feedback: Interact with the Monitor dashboards and provide data quality feedback for continuous improvement.	X	X	X	X	X	X
Attend Engagement and Training Events: Participate in engagement and training events to stay informed about best practices and updates ⁵¹ .	X	X	X	X	X	X
Reach Out for Help & Guidance: Contact the Monitor team for any issues or requests ⁵² .	X	X	X	X	X	X

Commented [CF109]: I would see policy makers as users of the Monitor, but not actively engaged in improving the quality of the Monitor. Again, what's the logic here?

Commented [GU110R109]: Reps from policy makers is more accurate, but we can remove that column if you prefer.

Commented [CF111R109]: For further discussion at the meeting

5.2 Indirect Improvement Strategies

The effective management and improvement of metadata within the OpenAIRE Graph require concerted efforts from all stakeholders in the research ecosystem. Recognizing the challenges identified in our metadata analysis, the following table presents a series

⁴⁸ <https://www.openaire.eu/validator-registration-guide>

⁴⁹ For details select "Researchers" in this page <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/how-it-works/the-5-monitors#tabs-content>

⁵⁰ <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/how-it-works/user-actions#upload>

⁵¹ <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/engagement-training>

⁵² <https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/contact-us>

of indirect strategies. **These are aimed at enhancing the overall quality and accuracy of data harvested into OpenAIRE.** By addressing key areas such as timely reporting, accurate metadata entry, and clear licensing, each stakeholder group plays a critical role in this process, and the recommended actions outlined below are tailored to leverage their unique positions and capabilities.

Table 23: Indirect Improvement Strategies for the Monitor

Stakeholder	Recommendation
Policy Makers	<p>Develop and enforce policies that mandate the registration and timely deposition of research outputs in national and international repositories, emphasizing the importance of accurate and standardized metadata.</p> <p>Develop and advocate for discipline-specific OA policies and support mechanisms.</p>
Publishers	<p>Implement consistent metadata standards across publications, particularly for identifying peer-review status, version of record, corresponding authors, and licensing information. Encourage open sharing of publication metadata to aid in more accurate data harvesting and indexing.</p> <p>Proactively share publication data, including APCs, BPCs, historical access rights of journals, and full-texts where possible to enhance the comprehensiveness and accuracy of the data available. Foster a culture of transparency and openness in licensing, ensuring clear communication of usage rights.</p>
RFOs	<p>Mandate and guide beneficiaries on accurate and timely reporting of project outcomes and publications, emphasizing the use of PIDs and standard metadata formats in their submissions.</p> <p>Advocate for and implement policies that require transparency in APC and BPC data from funded publications.</p>
RPOs	<p>Regularly review and update publication records in institutional repositories, focusing on the timeliness of deposits. Encourage researchers to use standard naming conventions and persistent identifiers (PIDs) for affiliations.</p> <p>Report APCs/BPCs to OpenAPC.</p>
Researchers	<p>Consistently use ORCID iDs in all research outputs, ensure timely updates of personal profiles in research databases, and accurately report affiliations and funding sources in publications.</p>
Institutional Repository Managers	<p>Adopt and adhere to the latest OpenAIRE guidelines for metadata.</p>

Stakeholder	Recommendation
Repository Managers (non-institutional)	Develop and maintain robust systems for metadata standardization and quality control. Ensure efficient and accurate handling of diverse research outputs, promoting consistency and completeness in metadata. Collaborate with primary data providers and other repositories to streamline data integration processes and jointly address metadata challenges. Adapt repository systems to accommodate and reflect historical changes in journal OA status. Implement, if not already present, automatic licensing functionalities in repositories.
All Stakeholders	Participate in training and engagement events to stay informed about best practices in metadata management and Open Science policies. Actively engage in community discussions to address common challenges and share solutions.

5.3 Long-Term Solutions

Shifting the focus to the future, this section outlines long-term solutions and workflow recommendations essential for the sustained advancement of OA monitoring. Drawing from the insights gained in our detailed metadata analysis, we propose strategies that address current challenges and try to anticipate evolving trends in research and data management. These recommendations are crafted to ensure the Open Access ecosystem is well-equipped to adapt, grow, and maintain high standards of data integrity and usefulness in the years to come.

Sustainable Data Management and Policy Enhancement (Policy Makers, RFOs, RPOs)

- Develop a framework for iterative improvement in metadata standards, building on identified metadata inconsistencies, to ensure relevance and effectiveness in capturing evolving research outputs.
- Advocate for policy harmonization across international platforms, focusing on standardizing metadata formats and PIDs, as highlighted by the analysis of ORCID iD coverage and publication data discrepancies.
- Promote global policy initiatives that resonate with the FAIR principles, facilitating a unified approach to Open Access data management.

Long-Term Data Preservation and Accessibility (Repository Managers, RPOs, and Data Curators)

- Implement strategies that adhere to the FAIR principles while considering future data accessibility needs, accounting for the rapid evolution of research dissemination methods.
- Establish or enhance national and international data repositories to comply with data preservation standards and adapt to changing data formats.

Routine Data Quality Audits and Collaborative Correction Processes (All Stakeholders):

- Institutionalize regular data audits to correct inconsistencies and gaps in metadata, such as affiliation, funding information, and licensing details.
- Create collaborative platforms for stakeholders to participate in metadata correction and enrichment, sharing expertise and resources.

Training, Capacity Building, and Feedback Loops (Policy Makers, Repository Managers RPOs/Librarians, Research Community Leaders):

- Conduct targeted training programs on metadata management areas identified as lacking, like licence reporting.
- Develop adaptive learning resources and feedback mechanisms to keep stakeholders updated with best practices and allow them to contribute to continuous metadata improvement.

By aligning these long-term solutions and workflow recommendations closely with the specific challenges and gaps identified in our metadata analysis, we ensure a data-driven and targeted approach. This strategy not only addresses current needs but also prepares for future challenges in Open Access monitoring and research data management.

6 Conclusion

The baseline analysis of the OA landscape in Ireland has revealed a complex and evolving picture. We observe significant strides toward embracing Open research practices, alongside areas that necessitate further attention and development. This conclusion synthesizes our key findings and reflections, offering a cohesive understanding of where Ireland stands with respect to Open Access uptake.

The scholarly production in Ireland, with a high proportion of peer-reviewed publications, underscores a commitment to academic rigor and quality. The growth in scholarly output over the years is indicative of a vibrant research environment, increasingly adopting digital practices such as DOIs and digital repositories.

In the realm of OA, while a considerable number of Irish publications are Open Access with licensing, a significant portion remains either without a license or under Closed Access. This situation reflects the ongoing transition in the Irish academic community toward fully Open research practices. The disparity in licensing across different publication types underscores the need for a more consistent approach to OA, particularly in publishing models like books and conference proceedings.

Publisher-mediated OA, encompassing Gold and Hybrid models, dominates the OA landscape in Ireland. This trend highlights the significant role of publishers in shaping OA practices. However, the growing presence of repository-mediated OA points to an evolving landscape where institutional and thematic repositories are gaining importance as complementary platforms for research dissemination.

The analysis of Plan S compliance has shown a predominant reliance on Gold OA with APCs. However, the increasing uptake of Transformative Agreements and journals, particularly in Social Sciences and humanities, suggests a strategic shift towards different OA models in these fields. This shift indicates a nuanced approach to OA adoption, reflecting the diverse needs and dynamics of various research disciplines.

Regarding APCs, the average cost per publication provides a baseline understanding of the financial aspect of OA publishing. However, the limited coverage of APC data underscores a need for greater transparency and more comprehensive reporting in this area. The variability in APCs across different scientific disciplines suggests differing financial pressures and publishing cultures in these fields.

Finally, the examination of FAIR principles and metadata completeness has brought to light the mixed landscape of licensing practices, with a blend of restrictive and open licenses. The widespread use of PIDs like DOIs and the increasing adoption of ORCID iDs are positive indicators of the Irish research community's move towards more streamlined and efficient scholarly communication. However, the quality and completeness of metadata remain areas for improvement to fully realize the benefits of open and accessible research.

The recommendations and solutions outlined in this report, spanning direct improvement strategies (via the Monitor functionalities available), indirect approaches, and long-term solutions, are aimed at fortifying OA monitoring and fostering a more robust, accurate, and efficient system. These strategies, derived from our analysis, offer practical steps for various stakeholders in the research ecosystem to collaboratively enhance the OA landscape in Ireland.

As we conclude this report, we reiterate the importance of ongoing efforts to refine and advance OA practices. The collective commitment of policymakers, publishers, researchers, RPOs, RFOs, repository managers and other stakeholders will be crucial in navigating the evolving challenges and opportunities in the world of scholarly communication.

7 Appendix

Institutional Repository Harvesting for the Monitor

(continued from Section 3.2)

In the first phase of the Monitor's development, attention was directed towards Institutional Repositories (IRs). These repositories were characterized using information from OpenDOAR, FAIRSharing registries, and those identified in the National Open Access Monitor, Ireland Survey. 8 institutional repositories were identified that had not been registered with OpenAIRE. Subsequently, we initiated the registration process and harvested their metadata records. Additionally, transformation rules were adjusted for each repository to custom transform metadata records, ensuring alignment with OpenAIRE Guidelines. The primary focus of these efforts was on crucial fields for the harvesting process and, where applicable, the identification of publications.

- PID
- Title
- Author
- Publication date
- Resource Type
- Access Rights

We successfully retrieved metadata from 7 of these repositories. However, one repository, identified as Obsolete in the Gap Analysis conducted by OpenAIRE in collaboration with the Irish NOAD in 2020 (Irish Health Publications Archive), was not harvested. Research@Thea, reported by two institutions in the survey (Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest and Atlantic Technological University), had 927 publications in its metadata records. Despite this, it is categorized as a Thematic Repository in OpenDOAR, providing metadata for multiple institutions. Additional refinement is necessary to register and harvest it into OpenAIRE. Affiliation matching for Research@Thea will be examined in the next phase, along with any other applicable repository types (such as ThematicPublication) Repositories.

The subsequent actions, in conjunction with the support of the "National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity" and in collaboration with the Irish network of repositories, will involve the identification and registration or selective harvesting of repositories/CRIS that are currently not registered. Additionally, an ensuing phase will focus on enhancing compatibility with the OpenAIRE Guidelines, upgrading to version 3.0 or, preferably, version 4.0. Moreover, we will concentrate on outreach activities to communicate with institutions whose metadata records we have aggregated. The aim is

Commented [CF112]: There have been a lot of National Open Access Monitor, Ireland surveys. The title of the relevant survey is "National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity"

to provide them with information about the process and encourage them to align with the OpenAIRE Guidelines. Concurrently, based on the National Open Access Monitor survey findings, several CRIS are currently in ongoing development. We plan to engage with these institutions, assessing their development progress, and establishing collaborations to ensure their inclusion in OpenAIRE and compliance with the OpenAIRE CRIS Guidelines.

OA Journals that are harvested through a compatible aggregator are not inherently linked to the institution or publisher within OpenAIRE. The subsequent actions involve institutions either registering their OA Journals in OpenAIRE or facilitating the registration and harvesting process. This is contingent upon the platforms supporting the OAI-PMH harvesting protocol. Alternatively, affiliations may be updated if these OA Journals have been associated with the institutions in the “National Open Access Monitor Survey: Organisational Identity.”

At this juncture, there is no necessity to proceed either with the utilization of the Metadata Validator to evaluate the completeness and FAIRness of metadata within records from repositories and OA Journals or with the OpenAIRE Broker service of enriching the original data sources. This is because the outcomes obtained would not accurately reflect the status of the records under examination. To ensure a more dependable assessment, we will revisit the implementation when we have a greater number of data sources (including repositories, CRIS, and OA Journals) registered in OpenAIRE and in compliance with the latest versions of the OpenAIRE Guidelines (v.3 and above). This decision will have no impact on the timelines/deliverables of the Monitor's release or the overall data quality within the Monitor. the OpenAIRE.Broker, to address enrichment of original data sources.

Commented [CF113]: Please include a disclaimer here that all such journal content will be associated with the organisation, as this may not be appropriate for all journals (not all authors will be authors of the institution).